

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

D3.2 Report on VITAL-5G integrated system and operational readiness results

Document Summary Information

Start Date	01/01/2021	Duration	36 months
Project URL	www.vital5g.eu		
Deliverable	D3.2 Report on VITAL-5G integrated system and operational readiness results		
Related Work Package	WP3	Related Task	T3.2, T3.3
Contractual due date	30/09/2022	Actual submission date	23/12/2022
Type	Report	Dissemination Level	Public
Deliverable Editor	Georgios Tsiouris (OTE)		

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Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	% Complete	Changes	Contributor(s)
v0.1	15/7/2022	3%	Initial ToC and assignments	Georgios Tsiouris (OTE), Marius Iordache (ORO)
v0.332	29/7/2022	10%	Initial input for RO testbed	Marius Iordache (ORO), Catalin Brezeanu(ORO), Oana Badita(ORO), Cosmin Schioapa(ORO)
v0.3	19/8/2022	15%	Initial input for BE testbed	Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac (IMEC), Vincent Charpentier (IMEC), Lian Xiangyu (TEL)
v0.4	26/8/2022	20%	Initial input for GR testbed	Georgios Tsiouris (OTE), Christos Ntogkas (WINGS), Ioannis Chondroulis (WINGS)
v0.5	16/9/2022	35%	Section 2 and Section 4 initial contributions	Marius Iordache (ORO), Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac (IMEC), Vincent Charpentier (IMEC), Andreas Gavrielides (eBOS)
v0.6	29/9/2022	50%	2 nd round of contributions for Sections 2,3,4	Marius Iordache (ORO), Catalin Brezeanu(ORO), Oana Badita(ORO), Cosmin Schioapa(ORO), Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac (IMEC), Vincent Charpentier (IMEC), Lian Xiangyu (TEL), Georgios Tsiouris (OTE), Christos Ntogkas (WINGS), Ioannis Chondroulis (WINGS)

v0.7	14/10/2022	60%	Contributions in Sections 4,5,6	Andreas Gavrielides (eBOS), Marius Iordache (Orange), Giada Landi (NXW), Juan Brenes (NXW), Gabriele Scivoletto (NXW), Christos Ntogkas (WINGS), Ioannis Chondroulis (WINGS)
v0.8	18/11/2022	75%	Contributions in Sections 6.2, 6.3, 6.4	Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac (IMEC), Vincent Charpentier (IMEC), Lian Xiangyu (TEL), Marius Iordache (Orange), Catalin Brezeanu (ORO), Oana Badita (ORO), Cosmin Schioapa (ORO), Georgios Tsiouris (OTE), Christos Ntogkas (WINGS), Ioannis Chondroulis (WINGS)
v0.85	13/12/2022	80%	Section 3. Integration Status, Annex I: Integration Plan	Georgios Tsiouris (OTE)
v0.9	13/12/2022	85%	Section 2. Platform Component Status	Georgios Tsiouris (OTE), Marius Iordache (ORO), Giada Landi (NXW), Juan Brenes (NXW), Gabriele Scivoletto (NXW), Christos Ntogkas (WINGS), Ioannis Chondroulis (WINGS), George Suci (BEIA), Alex Vulpe (BEIA), Andreas Gavrielides (eBOS)
v0.95	15/12/2022	95%	Executive Summary, Introduction, Conclusion, Editorial Changes	Georgios Tsiouris (OTE), Andreas Gavrielides (eBOS), Marius Iordache (ORO)
v0.96	17/12/2022	97%	Review from INCE, ATG	Athina Ropodi (INCE), Alina Beatrice Raileanu (ATG)
v0.97	18/12/2022	98%	Review comments implementation	Georgios Tsiouris (OTE), Marius Iordache (ORO), Christos Ntogkas (WINGS), Ioannis Chondroulis (WINGS), Eleni Giannopoulou (WINGS)
v0.98	21/12/2022	99%	TM, PC, WP3 Leader review	Giada Landi (NXW), Eleni Giannopoulou (WINGS), Marius Iordache (ORO)
v.0.99	22/12/2022	99%	Review comments implementation	Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac (IMEC), Vincent Charpentier (IMEC), Lian Xiangyu (TEL), Christos Ntogkas

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v1.0	23/12/2022	100%	Final formatting	Andreas Gavrielides (eBOS)

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Glossary of Terms and Abbreviations Used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5GC	5G Core
5G PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMC	Autonomic Management and Control
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
AN	Autonomous Networks
API	Application Programming Interface
APN	Access Point Name
AUSF	Authentication Server Function
CACC	Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control
CAPIF	Common API Framework
CB	Context Blueprint
CD	Continuous Deployment
CI	Continuous Integration
CNF	Container-based virtual Functions
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRUD	Create/Read/Update/Delete
CTXBs	Context Blueprints
DE	Decision-making-Element
DEV	Development
DNS	Domain Name System
E2E	End to End
EC	European Commission
ELCM	Experiment Life-Cycle Manager

eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EXPBs	Experiment Blueprints
EXPDs	Experiment Descriptors
Exp_ID	Experiment ID
GAN	Generic Autonomous Networking Architecture
gNB	gNodeB
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSMA	Global System for Mobile Association
GST	Global Slice Template
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HCI	Hyper Converged Infrastructure
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
HW	Hardware
ID	Identification
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IMSI	International Mobile Subscriber Identity
INT	Interoperability Testing
IoT	Internet of Things
ITU	International Telecommunications Union
IWF	Interworking Framework
K8s	Kubernetes
KNF	Kubernetes-based Network Function
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LTE	Long Term Evolution
LCM	LifeCycle Management
M2M	Machine to Machine

MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
mIoT	Massive IoT
ML	Machine Learning
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
MNOs	Mobile Network Operators
MQTT	MQ Telemetry Transport
NAB	Network App Blueprint
NBI	North-Bound Interface
NEF	Network Exposure Function
Network App	Network Application
NetOps	Network Operations
NF	Network Function
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NFVI	NFV Infrastructure
NFVO	NFV Orchestrator
NIC	Network Interface Card
NR	New Radio
NRF	NF Repository Function
NRS	Name Resolution Service
NS	Network Service
NSD	Network Service Descriptors
NSO	Network Services Orchestrator
NSSF	Network Slice Selection Function
NSSI	Network Slice Selection Assistance Information
OAS	Open API Specification
OEMs	Original Equipment Manufacturers
ONAP	Open Networking Automation Platform

OS	Operating System
OSM	Open Source MANO
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
PPDR	Public Protection and Disaster Relief
PPP	Public Private Partnership
PROD	Production
QoS	Quality Of Service
RAM	Random Access Memory
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technology
REST	Representational State Transfer
RRM	Radio Resource Management
RSRP	Reference Signal Received Power
SA	Standalone
SB	Service Blueprint
SBA	Service Based Architecture
SBI	South-Bound Interface
SCEF	Service Capability Exposure Function
SD	Slice Differentiator
SDN	Software Defined Radio
SEAL	Service Enabler Architecture Layer
SgNB	Secondary gNB
SINR	Signal to Interference & Noise Ratio
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SMF	Session Management Function
SotA	State-of-the-Art
SST	Slice/Service Type
SUPI	Subscription Permanent Identifier

S-NSSAI	Single Network Slice Selection Assistance information
SW	Software
T&L	Transport and Logistics
TaaS	Testing as a Service
TCB	Test Case Blueprint
TMV WG	Test Monitoring and Validation Work Group
UC	Use Case
UDM	Unified Data Management
UDR	Unified Data Repository
UE	User Equipment
UK	United Kingdom
UPF	User Plane Function
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything
VA	Vertical Agnostic
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager
VLAN	Virtual Local Area Network
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VNFD	VNF Descriptor
VNFM	VNF Manager
VS	Vertical Specific
VSB	Vertical Service Blueprint
VSD	Vertical Service Descriptor
VxFs	Veritas File System
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

One of the VITAL-5G objectives is to implement all the necessary upgrades and extensions onto the three 5G-testbeds and vertical Transport & Logistics (T&L) infrastructures, to be used in the extensive VITAL-5G trials. The required technical upgrades to the target 3GPP Rel.16 architecture have been described in detailed in D3.1 [5]. This deliverable is demonstrating that, at this stage, all the hardware and software components, for both the VITAL-5G centralized platform and the 5G testbeds have been deployed, implemented and integrated within an end-to-end functional scenario. These implementations allow the developers and experimenters, within the consortium or from 3rd parties, to onboard, provision, run and experiment with Network Applications on top of the enabled 5G infrastructure. In detail results are provided in the deliverable.

The VITAL-5G platform software components are implemented, on top of a dedicated virtualized infrastructure in the ORO testbed, in two flavours: Development, supporting the software components implementation, integration and testing activities, and the Production environment, the final VITAL-5G software components implementation. For clarity, the Production environment is based on the maturity of implementation of the components, after highly intensive tests performed in the Development area.

The validation is performed by using an integration and validation methodology that clearly certifies the successful platform components implementation, testing, validation and further integration with all the three testbeds, through the common platform infrastructure framework. The platform is deployed in high availability mode, as supported by the virtualized infrastructure in the ORO testbed, to guarantee the service continuity in case of failures on some VMs.

All the three 5G testbeds are deployed in the targeted architecture, with the main key network components being integrated and tested, from both the network functionality perspective (RAN, Core, Transport, Virtualization, Orchestration, Monitoring Plugins) but also from the network service level perspective. The testbeds are evaluated for the HW/SW integration and 5G SA end-to-end validation, as all the three testbeds are 5G SA network slicing capable (static configuration at this level), offering broadband or ultra-low-latency communication services to end-users and Network Application developers. Within all the experiments activities, there were validated also a large series of 5G SA capable devices, increasing the overall testbeds capabilities and opening the 3rd Parties experimentation path.

A particularly relevant implementation has been achieved by providing the multi-slice availability by using a single 5G SA device with a single subscriber provisioning, with the proper slice being selected at the device level based on the traffic requirements through network and device configuration.

The 5G testbeds are also integrated with the VITAL-5G Platform in a secured way through the defined interfaces for Slice management, Monitoring and Services orchestration. The activities for Network Application onboarding, lifecycle management, monitoring and experimental validation are performed from the VITAL-5G Platform, handling the interaction with each of the three testbeds through the implemented per-testbed plugins. In particular, plugins are available for Service and Network monitoring, Slice inventory and Service Orchestration for each testbed.

The results obtained during the intensive validation and integration activities for the VITAL-5G Platform and for the 5G testbed are concluding the successfully implementation of the 5G SA network in Belgium, Romanian and Greek testbed, the integration of the 2nd release of the Platform components (described and released in deliverable D2.3 [3]) with the testbed and the services functionality.

1. Introduction

The VITAL-5G project integration activities are split into three parts. The first is the integration of the software components of the VITAL-5G platform itself, the second is the integration of the VITAL-5G Platform with the three testbeds and the third is the internal integration inside each of the three testbeds. The platform core elements were integrated early in the lifetime of the project forming the Drop I which was released in M15 and was used as a basis for further integration and development for both the rest of the platform components and the three testbeds.

The second release of the VITAL-5G platform i.e., Drop II released in deliverable D2.3 [3], is the first release fully integrated with the three testbeds' management functions for the monitoring, slicing and orchestration, thus enabling a complete and totally functional system which can be used for trials within the consortium or for 3rd party experiments. This release of the VITAL-5G system also includes the internal integrations of each testbed i.e., the 5G Core integration and the management functions integration with the lower parts of each one of the testbeds.

Regarding the integration planning, this was organized into the splitting of the main workflow functions of the system, i.e., the Network App Package onboarding, the Vertical Service instantiation and the Experiment creation, execution and monitoring, into weekly Sprints of work to better organize the timing and order of the integration process. The planning includes the integration of the VITAL-5G platform with the northbound interfaces of the testbeds mediated by the per-testbed plugins for service orchestration, network slice management and network/service monitoring.

All the main workflows are integrated both at platform level and at the northbound interface level with the testbeds forming a complete system, ready for the 3rd parties' experimenters to start experimenting with the platform. The internal testbed integrations are also ready, all of them offering 3GPP Rel. 16 5G connectivity with slicing and monitoring support. The orchestration management functions are integrated with the underlying virtualization infrastructures of each testbed and the southbound interfaces of the centrally located platform in Orange Romania. The monitoring and slicing management functions of all testbeds are also integrated with the platform and the underlying infrastructure of each testbed.

The development and testing phases of the VITAL-5G platform and testbeds were planned around three distinct phases, named Drop I, II and III. Each Drop has different targets for component integration and testing, and it derives from the software development plan defined in WP2 and initially reported in D2.1 [2]. This plan specifies the components available in each software release of the VITAL-5G platform and its functionalities, providing high level guidelines for the list of modules and features to be integrated in each drop. Moreover, the integration plan has been built on the basis of the components' interfaces and the general workflows for Network App Package Onboarding, Vertical Service Instantiation and Experiment Creation, Execution and Monitoring, as described in deliverables D1.2 [1], D2.1 [2] and D2.3 [3].

This is the first integration deliverable and provides the VITAL-5G platform and testbed integration status up to now and including Drop II. The reader should first get acquainted with the D1.2 [1], D2.1 [2] and D2.3 [3] deliverables, where the architecture, workflows, component implementation specifics, functionality and interfaces between components are described. This deliverable will serve as a guide on how the integration methodology was implemented up to Drop II of the VITAL-5G platform, how the Network Applications (Network Apps) were onboarded and how the Vertical Services can be instantiated followed by a description on how the user will be able to create, execute and monitor an experiment. The deliverable offers a concise description of the northbound interfaces of the testbeds (Belgian, Romanian and Greek), as well as the associated plugins.

Furthermore, a detailed description of the VITAL-5G testbeds is provided, explaining how the 5G RAN and 5G Core were tested and integrated and, wherever applicable, how the slicing was tested. Finally, we provide a brief overview of how the testing methodology was adapted in this Drop with more details being presented in D3.3 due in M30, referring to the final release of the VITAL-VITAL-VITAL-5G system.

The successful implementation of the components is demonstrated in this deliverable through a series of relevant outputs from the 5G testbeds or VITAL-5G components, outputs that are proving our full networks and services implementation.

1.1. Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map VITAL-5G’s Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed.

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
Task 3.2 VITAL-5G system components integration	The VITAL-5G experimentation facility is a multi-component structure comprised of existing, upgraded 5G testbeds (T3.1), vertical facilities and equipment (T3.1), open virtual platform and repository (T2.2) and NetApps (T2.1) and vertical intelligent applications (T2.4), which are all developed in different tasks. This task will be responsible for the end-to-end integration of all these heterogeneous components into one single, smoothly functioning system, guaranteeing the interoperability and cooperation of the different HW and SW elements and delivering a functional experimentation facility.	Section 3. Integration Status	Describes the integration status of the VITAL-5G platform with respect to the three testbeds.
		Section 4. Common Platform Infrastructure	Describes the common platform infrastructure status for running the VITAL-5G platform.
		Section 5. Testbed Components Integration and Testing	Describes the integration between the testbed components with particular emphasis to the standalone 5G Cores, orchestration and management.
		Section 6. Platform and Testbed Integration	Describes the integration of the testbeds with the VITAL-5G platform.
Task 3.3 VITAL-5G platform functional testing and operational readiness	The aim of this task is to conduct preliminary functional acceptance tests to assess the performance of the VITAL-5G Platform and technically validate its proper operation including the 5G network infrastructure, so as to reduce the ambiguities prior to field trial use case validation. These initial trials will perform functional testing on each of the Platform’s components to ensure that they are operationally ready	Section 444. First full-release of the VITAL-5G platform is operational in production environment	Describes the VITAL-5G Platform deployment in the VMs installed in production environment

	<p>for the trials. Dry runs will be performed to benchmark the performance of the system against target network and application-level KPIs. The intention is to achieve a fully functional Platform providing an environment suitable for NetApps and use case testing and validation</p>		
DELIVERABLE			
D3.2 Report on VITAL-5G integrated system & operational readiness results.			

1.2. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This deliverable is split into the following sections:

Section 2 describes the platform component status and their availability to the production system.

Section 3 describes the integration status of the VITAL-5G platform with the three testbeds.

Section 4 describes the common platform virtual infrastructure status for running the centralized VITAL-5G platform deployed in ORO testbed.

Section 5 describes the integration between the testbed components with particular emphasis to the standalone 5G Cores, the orchestration of each testbed and its integration with the virtualized environments.

Section 6 describes the integration of the testbeds with the VITAL-5G platform and in particular the monitoring, slicing and orchestration integration with the platform.

Finally, the document concludes with the presentation of the integration plan in Annex I: Integration Plan.

2. Platform Component Status

The platform component status is shown in Table 1 and describes the VITAL-5G components status and their production deployment status as of the date of submission of this deliverable. In this chapter, we describe the general Architecture components status, starting with the software component of the Portal Web GUI to the component for Multi-Slice Inventory, as presented further in Table 1.

The VITAL-5G platform components are fully implemented, as demonstrated by the VITAL-5G availability in the production environment, through which all the validation tests have been performed. The overall functionality and detailed description of each one of the components is detailed in D2.1 [2] and the set of features available on the first-full-release (M23) is described in D2.3 [3], concluding the successful platform components integration, as per details presented in Annex I: Integration Plan, the status flow of the Integration Plan and the sprint analysis of the following: Network App Package Onboarding, Vertical Services Instantiation, Experiment Creation, Execution and Monitoring, and the Delivery Plans for testbed northbound interface and adaptation plugins.

Table 1: Platform Component Status

Architecture Component	SW Components	Completion Status	Responsible Partner	Production
Portal Web GUI	Portal Web GUI	100%	eBOS	Yes
Network App Catalogue	Network Apps, Services and Experiment Catalogue	100%	NXW	Yes
Service Catalogue				
Experiment Catalogue				
Vertical Services LCM	Service LCM	100%	NXW	Yes
Network App Validator	Network App Validator	100%	BEIA	Yes
Blueprint Validation Tool				
Service Testing & Experiment Manager	Experiment LCM	100%	NXW	Yes
Result Analytics	Result Analytics	100%	WINGS	Yes
AI-based Diagnostics	AI-based Diagnostics	100%	WINGS	Yes
Service & Network Monitoring	Monitoring Platform	100%	IMEC	Yes
Multi-Site 5G Slice Inventory	Slice Manager	100%	IMEC	Yes
Multi-site Inventory	Multi-site Inventory	100%	NXW	Yes

All the above architecture components are at a “First full drop features” level, as described in D2.3 [3]. To be more specific, the features per components are:

- **The Portal Web GUI:** onboarding Network Apps and vertical services, presentation of Network Apps and vertical services in GUI, vertical service LCM support, ability to onboard experiments, supporting OAuth, permitting visualization of site device inventory, 5G slice instances available in the slice inventory, monitoring network, compute resources, as well as platform metrics through Grafana¹ dashboards.
- **Network Apps, Services & Experiments Catalogue:** onboarding/query/removal of Network App packages and blueprints, Vertical Service Blueprints and Descriptors (VSB/VSD)), and Experiment Blueprints and Descriptors (EXPB/EXPD); onboarding of VNF packages and NSDs into OSM NFV Orchestrators; integration of automatic Network App validation.
- **Vertical Services LCM:** vertical service lifecycle management, with provisioning, configuration and termination actions, triggered via REST API with OAUTH integration, integration with AI-based Analytics and Diagnostics Tools, support for OSM Day2 primitives.
- **Network App Validator and Blueprint Validation Tool:** validation of NetApp blueprints in JSON format; validation of sensor data used by Network Apps and supported dynamic KPI monitoring; availability of OpenAPI REST interfaces for other components compatibility.
- **Service Testing & Experiment Manager:** lifecycle management for experiment creation/execution/termination, access through OAUTH, integration with AI-based diagnostics and analytics, support for Test Cases and Experiment Definition, support for OSM Day2 primitives, definition of advanced test cases.
- **Result Analytics:** network, infrastructure, platform and service metrics ingestion from the Monitoring Platform; KPI calculation; Statistical Analysis on gathered data; threshold generation for results validation; interaction with Vertical Service LCM in the closed-control loop.
- **AI-based diagnostics:** metrics and generated KPIs ingestion; performance degradation and anomaly detection; anomaly root-cause analysis; Vertical Service LCM interfacing for event propagation as part of the closed control loop mechanism.
- **Service & Network Monitoring:** topics configuration (simple and dynamic) for network, infrastructure, platform and services KPIs; collection of ZeroMQ² queues in real-time; unified interface towards VITAL-5G testbed monitoring modules for data gathering and metric configuration; Grafana monitoring dashboard; diagnostics event distribution through topics.
- **Multi-Site 5G Slice Inventory:** slice catalogue management through REST API, unified SBI for slice lifecycle management, NBI for 5G slice querying and allocation towards the VITAL-5G platform components.
- **Multi-Site Inventory:** per-site device catalogue management; per-site NFVO information and query; per-site monitoring agent information management and querying; per-site Monitoring Agent information management and querying.

¹ <https://grafana.com/>

² <https://zeromq.org/>

3. Integration Status

The development and testing phase were designed around three distinct phases, named Drop I, II and III. Each Drop has different targets for component integration and testing, following the software development plan described in D2.1 [2] for the VITAL-5G platform. Each Drop is defined by the components to be integrated as well as the general workflows described in the relevant architecture deliverables. This section describes the integration methodology, the integration status of the VITAL-5G platform and its integration with the three testbeds.

3.1. Integration Methodology

The integration plan, as shown in Figure 1, comprises the Workflow Level Status Dashboards, the Testbeds Level Delivery Plans, the Overall Workflows Delivery Plan and the Components and Infrastructure Status.

The general architecture workflows presented in D1.2 [1], i.e., the Network App Package Onboarding, the Vertical Service Instantiation and the Experiment creation, execution and monitoring are analysed into one-week sprints of integration work, are combined into groups of sprints, and represent the Workflow Level Status Dashboards of the project. These workflow dashboards monitor the integration of the platform components and the integration of the platform itself with the three testbeds.

The Testbed Level Status Dashboards are exclusively deduced from the Workflow Level Status Dashboard Sprints and they give a detailed status of each testbed. These Dashboards monitor the work in a very detailed manner, including the testbed plugins required to integrate each testbed with the VITAL-5G Platform. The Dashboards are designed in such a way to be able to add specific testbed sprints and dive into the testbed specific parts, i.e., internal testbed integration efforts.

The Overall Workflows Delivery Plan represents the overall integration status of the project, i.e., the integration status of the VITAL-5G platform and the three testbeds. It is deduced from the Workflow Status Dashboards and the Testbed Status Dashboards.

The VITAL-5G Components and Infrastructure status has a description of the status of all platform components, testbed infrastructure and plugins and it is loosely coupled with the Workflow Level Status Dashboards, in the sense that the sprint reporting should be compatible with the development status of the actual components and vice versa.

Figure 1: Integration Plan Overview.

3.2. Workflow Level Status

In this section, the status of the Network App Package Onboarding, Vertical Service Instantiation and Experiment Creation, Execution and Monitoring will be presented.

3.2.1. Network App Package Onboarding

The Network App Package Onboarding workflow, which has been presented in D1.2 [1], details the onboarding of a Network App Package through the Portal Web GUI. The latter interacts with the platform for onboarding, retrieval, deletion and validation of the Network App package. The VSB and the NSD onboarding, retrieval deletion and validation were part of the Drop I of the platform which was available at the beginning of April 2022. The VNF package onboarding to the OSM of the three testbeds was concluded in the beginning of September 2022, while the Network App package onboarding and validation was concluded at the end of December 2022. For more details for the individual testbed delivery plans and their break up into Sprints please refer to the relevant part of Annex I: Integration Plan.

3.2.2. Vertical Services Instantiation

The Vertical Services Instantiation workflow, which has been presented in D1.2 [1], details the Vertical Service instantiation and its lifecycle management. The core platform-level operations were available for the early Drop of the platform (Drop I) by the end of March 2022.

The actual instantiation of a Vertical Service to the testbeds through the Portal Web GUI, which also includes deployment, slicing, monitoring, and visualisation of the Vertical Services information were available at the end of November 2022 and is related to the Drop II of the VITAL-5G platform. For more details for the individual testbed delivery plans and their break up into Sprints please refer to the relevant part of Annex I: Integration Plan.

3.2.3. Experiment Creation, Execution and Monitoring

The Experiment Creation, Execution and Monitoring workflow, which has been presented in D1.2 [1], details the experiment definition, creation, execution, monitoring and clean-up operations.

Drop I contained the initial core platform lifecycle management operations and was available from the beginning of March 2022. Drop II, contains the experiment definition, creation and execution, monitoring and clean-up through the Portal Web GUI to the three testbeds and is available since mid-November 2022. For more details for the individual testbed delivery plans and their break up into Sprints please refer to the relevant part of Annex I: Integration Plan.

3.3. Testbed Northbound Interface and Adaptation Plugins

All testbeds are fully integrated with the platform. The latest integrated workflow is the Experiment Creation, Execution and Monitoring.

The slicing integration for Drop II is limited in scope with statically created slices in each testbed. The northbound slicing plugin interfaces have the same API, which is presented in section 6.1 although their southbound interface differs depending on the 5G Core implementation. All testbeds will be upgraded to dynamic slicing for Drop III. For more details for the individual testbed delivery plans and their break up into Sprints please refer to the Annex I, section Annex I: Integration Plan.

3.4. Overall Integration Status

Table 2 summarizes the overall status of the integration activities for the features planned for Drop I and Drop II. The Drop II together with the testbed integrations finished in mid-December 2022.

Table 2: Overall Integration Status.

Task description	Progress
Drop I (M15)	100%
Network App Package Onboarding at the platform level	100%
Vertical Service Instantiation at the platform level	100%
Experiment Definition at the platform level	100%
Drop II (M23)	100%
Workflow 1 Network App Package Onboarding	100%
VNF Package Onboarding	100%
Network App Package Onboarding	100%
Workflow 2 Vertical Services Instantiation	100%
Vertical Service Instantiation	100%
Dynamic Slice Management (full support planned for Drop III)	30%
Static Slice Management	100%
Vertical Service Deployment in the three testbeds	100%
Monitoring	100%
Workflow 3 Experiment Creation Execution & Monitoring	100%
Experiment Definition	100%
Experiment Creation	100%
Experiment Execution	100%
Experiment Monitoring	100%
Experiment Cleanup	100%
Testbed delivery plans	100%
Drop II (M23)	100%
Bucharest Testbed	100%
Antwerp Testbed	100%
Greek Testbed	100%

4. Common Platform Infrastructure

The VITAL-5G Platform software components are hosted at the ORO testbed in a dedicated High-Availability VMWare Cluster’s infrastructure, by providing secured platform’s access to the developers and experimenters, as described in D3.1 [5] and protected by security by design mechanisms provided by ORO, respecting today’s strict security rules and recommendations.

Figure 2: VITAL-5G Platform testbed and developers secured access.

The VITAL-5G Platform infrastructure is deployed in two flavours, the PROD (Platform operation in production) and DEV (Platform for development implementation, integration and testing). The status of VMs completion is described by Table 3. We have implemented a clear domain separation between DEV and PROD, as described in the next Table, uniquely identifying the VITAL-5G Platform VMs in the two flavours:

- Development (DEV) and Production (PROD);
- status of VMs deployment (100% for all);
- software modules already running within the VMs;
- virtual resource requirements of each VM deployment;
- network separation of the VMs, between two network addressing schemes, one for the DEV environment and one for the PROD environment.

Table 3: VITAL-5G Platform status of VMs completion.

VM No	VM Name		Modules	Requirements	Network Addressing	
	DEV	PROD			DEV	PROD
VM #1	vital5g-catalog-DEV	vital5g-catalog-PROD	Network Apps, Services & Experiments Catalogue - Service LCM - Experiment LCM - License Manager - Multi-site Inventory	vCPU: 8 RAM: 8 GB Disk: 50 GB OS: Ubuntu Server 18.4	172.28.18.98	172.28.18.66
VM #2			Portal Web GUI	vCPU: 8	172.28.18.99	172.28.18.67

	vital5g-portal-DEV	vital5g-portal-PROD		RAM: 8 GB Disk: 50 GB OS: Ubuntu Server 18.4		
VM #3	vital5g-diagnostics-DEV	vital5g-diagnostics-PROD	Results Analytics, AI-based Diagnostic Intent-based Requests Manager	CPU: 8 RAM: 8 GB Disk: 40 GB OS: Ubuntu Server 18.4	172.28.18.100	172.28.18.68
VM #4	vital5g-slice-inventory-DEV	vital5g-slice-inventory-PROD	Slice Inventory Monitoring Platform (Data Collection Manager)	CPU: 8 RAM: 8 GB Disk: 120 GB OS: Ubuntu Server 18.4	172.28.18.101	172.28.18.69
VM #5	vital5g-monitoring-DEV	vital5g-monitoring-PROD	Monitoring Platform (Data Collection Storage)	CPU: 4 RAM: 8 GB Disk: 50 GB OS: Ubuntu Server 18.4	172.28.18.102	172.28.18.70
VM #6	vital5g-validator-DEV	vital5g-validator-PROD	Blueprint Validation Tool Network App Validator	CPU: 4 RAM: 8 GB Disk: 30 GB OS: Ubuntu Server 18.4	172.28.18.103	172.28.18.71
VM #7	vital5g-access-DEV	vital5g-access-PROD	Access Control	CPU: 4 RAM: 8 GB Disk: 30 GB OS: Ubuntu Server 18.4	172.28.18.104	172.28.18.72

The VITAL-5G platform is hosted on a dedicated Node Infrastructure Cluster, deploying the VMs in High Availability mode, as in Table 4, through two medium performance compute nodes, running the platform on top of the VMWare virtualization software. We have created separated virtualized infrastructure domains inside the Romanian testbed: (1) to host the VITAL-5G Platform (VMWare) and (2) to host all Network Application components developed in the project (SSOpenStack³).

Table 4: VITAL-5G Node Infrastructure Cluster characteristics.

node10.ngnetworks.orange.intra	node10.ngnetworks.orange.intra
Hypervisor: VMware ESXi, 7.0.3, 18644231 Model: ProLiant DL380 Gen10 Processor Type: Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4116 CPU @ 2.10GHz Logical Processors: 48 NICs: 8 State: Connected Uptime: 161 days	Hypervisor: VMware ESXi, 7.0.3, 18644231 Model: ProLiant DL380 Gen10 Processor Type: Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4116 CPU @ 2.10GHz Logical Processors: 48 NICs: 8 State: Connected Uptime: 161 days

The VITAL-5G Platform components described in Table 5 are fully identified within the deployed infrastructure, i.e., being identified from the hosting cluster, as seen below:

Table 5: VITAL-5G Platform vSphere Client of VMs deployment.

vSphere Client VMs deployment	ESXI Cluster Information								
<p>The screenshot shows the vSphere Client interface with a search bar at the top. Below the search bar, there are icons for Home, Recent, Datastores, and Networks. A list of VMs is displayed, with 'vcenter5glab-bi20221' selected. Other VMs include vital5g-access-DEV, vital5g-access-PROD, vital5g-catalog-DEV, vital5g-catalog-PROD, vital5g-diagnostics-DEV, vital5g-diagnostics-PROD, vital5g-monitoring-DEV, vital5g-monitoring-PROD, vital5g-portal-DEV, vital5g-portal-PROD, vital5g-slice-inventory-DEV, vital5g-slice-inventory-PROD, vital5g-validator-DEV, vital5g-validator-PROD, vital5g-vrf01-vm, and vital5g-vrf02-vm.</p>	<p>vcenter5glab-bi20221</p> <p>Guest OS: Ubuntu Linux (64-bit) Compatibility: ESXi 7.0 U2 and later (VM version 19) VMware Tools: Running, version:2147483647 (Guest Managed) DNS Name: vital5g-<VM-name> IP Addresses: IP class</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Cluster</td> <td>BI20221-ESXI-CLUSTER</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Host</td> <td>5glab-node11.ngnetworks.orange.intra</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Networks</td> <td>DPG-VLAN341-</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Storage</td> <td>Datastore-NFS-5GLAB</td> </tr> </table>	Cluster	BI20221-ESXI-CLUSTER	Host	5glab-node11.ngnetworks.orange.intra	Networks	DPG-VLAN341-	Storage	Datastore-NFS-5GLAB
Cluster	BI20221-ESXI-CLUSTER								
Host	5glab-node11.ngnetworks.orange.intra								
Networks	DPG-VLAN341-								
Storage	Datastore-NFS-5GLAB								

³ <https://www.openstack.org/>

Lastly, we have evaluated the total infrastructure’s resources required for the VITAL-5G Platform deployment and implementation, for future platform implementation in different environments, such as Private or Public Clouds (see Table 6).

Table 6: VITAL-5G Platform computing required resources.

CPU	RAM	Storage	Network Interfaces	Computes nodes (HA)
44 vCPU	56 GB	370 GB	1	2

After the integration of the VITAL-5G Platform components, the system has been successfully moved on the production environment. In the following figures, as an example, we show the status of one of the VMs deployed in production and some screenshots of the VITAL-5G platform GUI running in production.

Figure 3: VITAL-5G Portal VM running in production environment.

Figure 4: VITAL-5G Portal VM – Example of CLI output demonstrating its network connectivity in the virtual environment

Figure 5: VITAL-5G Portal web GUI on production environment – main page

Figure 6: VITAL-5G Portal web GUI on production environment – Catalogue of Network Applications.

Net Apps Blueprint Details

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Field	Value
Name	VA4 IoT Management Platform
Version	1.0
Description	NetApp for collection of IoT data and actuators control for heterogeneous and configurable devices, with mechanisms for unified data modelling, monitoring, and reporting.
Testbed	ATHENS
Access Level	PUBLIC
Spec Level	VERTICAL_AGNOSTIC
Type	SERVICE
Placements	CORE
Components	IoTAlertAndEventManager (core) IoTSupervisor (core) MessageBroker (core) DatastoreAndDashboard (core) RestController (core)
Endpoints	alertEventManager, INTERNAL datastoreDashboardQuery, EXTERNAL messageBrokerCore, INTERNAL
5G Endpoints	IoTSupervisorData, Slice Profile: URLLC, Params: [availability: 99], [latency: 60]
Application Metrics	Alarm Rate

Figure 7: VITAL-5G Portal web GUI on production environment – Details of a Network Application.

5. Testbed Components Integration and Testing

The 5G SA "testbed's components integration and testing status is described by Table 7 and further demonstrated in the specific testbeds chapters, following the plans and upgrades to the target architecture described in D3.1 [5].

In all three testbeds, we have upgraded the OSM to version 12 in order to avoid a series of orchestration bugs identified with the previous version (OSM R10) during the integration processes and workflows, experimented upon using continuously the VITAL-5G platform on the testbeds. The summary presented in the table is highlighting the actual 5G SA testbed components status for the 5G Hardware (HW) and Software (SW) integration and end-to-end (E2E) 5G services, the 5G RAN and Core in VITAL-5G testbeds are following the targeted 3GPP Rel.16.

Table 7: VITAL-5G testbed components integration and testing status

Testbed	Status HW/SW (%) 3GPP Rel16	RAN gNB	5GCN Comp.	Transport network	Slicing eMBB/ URLLC	Orchestration OSMv12	Monitoring Internal Probes
Antwerp	HW/SW Integration	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%
	5G E2E Validation	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%
Bucharest	HW/SW Integration	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%
	5G E2E Validation	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%
Greek	HW/SW Integration	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%
	5G E2E Validation	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%	Yes 100%

More details about the testbeds technical design and 5G SA architecture implemented are described in D3.1 [5].

5.1. Belgian Testbed

The updated overview of the 5G testbed characteristics for the Antwerp site is presented in Table 8. As it can be seen, all major components of the testbed, i.e., NFV infrastructure, 5G Radio, Core, and Transport, including monitoring and slice inventory capabilities, have been fully finalised. Thus, this 5G testbed is ready for the full trialling activities in the Antwerp trial site and the Assisted Vessel Transport use case, as well as for the trialling activities that will be performed by the third-party experimenters.

Table 8: Belgian testbed status.

Type	Description	Completion Status	Version	Features
NFV Infrastructure	OpenStack Kubernetes ⁴ Docker ⁵	100%	OpenStack Ussuri Kubernetes release 1.26.0 Docker v20.10. 21	Virtualization of computing resources that are used for deploying Network Apps
Orchestration	OSM	100%	v12 (v10 running as backup)	Management and orchestration of Network Apps and vertical services
5G RAN	2 new builds + 2 upgrades	100%	v1.0 ⁶	4x4MIMO, 3 slices (default, streaming, low latency)
5G CORE	5G SA core	100%	v0.9	AMF, SMF, UPF, AUSF, etc.
5G Network Transport	E2E connectivity	100%	v0.9	E2E slicing
5G SA validated devices	1xphone (Oppo Find X5 Pro) + 1x CPE (Peplink Dome)	100%	NA	SA attach and slicing attach by APN. PDU activation by traffic type
5G network monitoring	Real-time collection of network, service, infrastructure, and platform KPIs	100%	v0.1	Local monitoring platform running at the 5G edge, interfacing with the centralized monitoring platform
5G network slicing	5G SA network E2E Network slicing (3GPP)	100%	v0.1	Static network slicing available (predefined network slices), including partially dynamic

⁴ <https://kubernetes.io/>

⁵ <https://www.docker.com/>

⁶ Versions of the 5G RAN, Core, and Transport Network, which are stated in this document, reflect on the current progress of deploying radio, core, and transport features, and the difference in versions between successive deliverables shows the progress on creating additional network features. The real versions of those components are considered confidential by vendors (Nokia and Ericsson), and as such cannot be shared in the deliverable.

			network slicing that will be further detailed in Drop IIIIIII
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5.1.1. 5G RAN and 5G Core integration and testing, 5G Slicing Testing

As mentioned in the 5G network design, the overall integration of 5G SA radio and 5G core is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Telenet 5G RAN & Core integration for NSA & SA.

As shown in Figure 8, on the RAN side both 5G SA and 5G NSA share the same tower infrastructure, cabinets, and power supply. The 5G SA cell is radiated by only N78 TDD RU, while the 5G NSA network is radiated by both N78 TDD RU and N1 FDD RU. The NR N1 is configured as DSS with LTE B1 to share the total 15MHz bandwidth. The baseband processing hardware between 5G SA and 5G NSA are also shared. The key to isolating the two RAN environments is by introducing a de-core function on the RAN. On the transmission side, DSCP values for IP transmission priority are configured to map 5QI values of different network slices. The 5G SA DSCP values are created as new ones, on top of DSCP values for legacy technology. On the core side, there are three core networks configured to work in Port of Antwerp cluster. The production EPC is handling legacy 4G traffic from production network, together with control plane messages for production 5G NSA network. For 5G NSA users, their service is managed by production EPC, production 5GC and production 5G NSA radio. For 5G SA trial users accessing the Antwerp testbed, they access 5G NR and trial 5GC. Note that the 5G SA trial users have full priority on RAN, transmission and they are isolated at the core level. This is to secure the 5G SA network performance and make 5G NSA part a nice to have in the area.

5.1.1.1. RAN Integration

The 5G network slicing parameters for the SA cell are integrated into RAN configuration. Each 5QI label is created according to the slicing design. For example, 5QI 8 for the default eMBB slice is configured as follows:

```
crn GNBCUUPFunction=1,CUUP5qiTable=Default,CUUP5qi=qi8
aqmMode 1
counterActiveMode false
dcDlPdcPAggrPrioCg 3
dcDlPdcPAggrTimeDiffCg 2
dcDlPdcPAggrTimeDiffProhibit 200
dcDlPdcPAggrTimeDiffThresh 150
dscp 12
estimatedE2ERTT 50
packetDelayBudget 280
packetDelayBudgetOffset 0
profile5qi 8
t0ooUldelivery 150|
userLabel
end
commit
```

Figure 9: eMBB slice configuration.

The de-core function on RAN will identify different SIM profiles and connect to different cores. Note that the configuration allows 5G SA cell traffic to always take priority over 5G NSA traffic. Thus, the NR resource can be considered 100% available for VITAL-5G SA trials.

5.1.1.2. Core Integration

As shown in Figure 8, the Antwerp testbed 5G core is a dedicated 5G trial core. The core supports 5G SA only and both user plane data and control plane data of 5G SA UEs are routed through the SA cell to reach the Trial 5G core. From the currently supported 5QI, the network slices are defined in the first implementation according to the use case analysis and architecture design reported in D1.1 [6] and summarized in Table 9.

Table 9: Antwerp testbed 5G trial core NSSAI definition.

Slice Name	IoT “S-NSSAI-1”	eMBB “S-NSSAI-2”	URLLC “S-NSSAI-3”
SST, SD	SST = 1, SD = 3	SST = 1, SD = 2	SST = 2, SD = 1
GBR type	NGBR + NGBR	NGBR+GBR	NGBR+GBR
Session and Service Continuity support	SSC mode 1	SSC mode 1	SSC mode 1
Slice quality of service	5QI 8 / 9	5QI 8 / 4	5QI 8 / 65
Latency Budget	100ms / 100ms	100 ms / 50ms	100ms / 20ms
APN / DNN	IoT	live-stream	URLLC
Trigger type	Network App server IP	Network App server IP and traffic type	Network App server IP and traffic type

For all network slices, the default 5QI value 8 is always selected by default. Depending on the use case requirements, the trigger to dedicated 5QI within the slices is different. Note that on top of the slices above, the default network slice is configured with only 5QI value 8 and automatic APN setting (5g-internet) in the SIM card.

The “S-NSSAI-1” IoT slice, is defined as the basic 5G data service slice, with only 5QI value 8 configured on the default DNN. The default 5QI for any DNN/network slice must be non-GBR. The 5QI value 9 is the dedicated QoS for IoT slice. This value has lower priority than the default 5QI 8.

The “S-NSSAI-2” eMBB slice is a dedicated network slice defined for camera streams. Same as other slices the default 5QI value is 8. Once the network detects the UDP traffic towards predefined IP destinations, which in the Antwerp testbed is the IP of Antwerp NetApp servers, new PDU sessions are created with 5QI value 4 for the camera streams, while other traffic types from the same 5G UE or SIM remain on default 5QI 8.

The “S-NSSAI-3” URLLC is the network slice for low latency services. Same as other slices the default 5QI value is 8. Once the network detects ICMP or UDP traffic towards predefined IP destinations, which in the Antwerp testbed is the IP of Antwerp NetApp servers which are mission-critical sensor servers, the new PDU session will activate the 5QI 65.

```
[cmm@cmu-necc0 ~]$ cmm snssai list
+-----+
| snssai |
+-----+
| NSSAI-1 |
| NSSAI-2 |
| NSSAI-3 |
+-----+
[cmm@cmu-necc0 ~]$
[cmm@cmu-necc0 ~]$
[cmm@cmu-necc0 ~]$
[cmm@cmu-necc0 ~]$
[cmm@cmu-necc0 ~]$ cmm snssai show NSSAI-3
+-----+-----+
| Field | Value |
+-----+-----+
| snssai | NSSAI-3 |
| name* | NSSAI-3 |
| sliceServiceType | 2 |
| sliceDifferentiator | 000001 |
| supportedInAllTa | true |
+-----+-----+
```

Figure 10: Configured NSSAIs on Antwerp testbed.

```
A:AN0990-CMU-SMF01>config>mobile>profile# info
-----
list
  plmn "homeplmn"
    mcc 206 mnc 05
    mcc 206 mnc 20
    mcc 206 mnc 21
  exit
  prioritized-ip-address-list "amf"
    address 10.101.37.213 port 8080
  exit
  prioritized-ip-address-list "udmsdm"
    address 10.101.37.221
  exit
  prioritized-ip-address-list "udmuecm"
    address 10.101.37.220
  exit
  slice-list "slicelist1"
    slice NSSAI-1 sst 1 sd 000001
    exit
    slice NSSAI-2 sst 1 sd 000002
    exit
    slice NSSAI-3 sst 2 sd 000001
    exit
  exit
```

Figure 11: Antwerp Testbed SMF configuration.

In total, 100 SIMs are provisioned on the 5G trial core to access network slicing. The SIM profiles are defined in three catalogues as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Example of SIM profile configured on Antwerp testbed.

After the end-to-end integration of RAN and core, 5G SA test users can register on network slices with APN configuration. An example of a 5G SA UE attached on network slice S-NSSAI-2 is shown below:

```
A:AN0990-CMU-SMF01# show mobile-gateway pdn pdn-context supi 206059899018004 detail
=====
PDN context detail
=====
SUPI      : 206059899018004
DNN       : live-stream
Public DNN : N/A
Virtual DNN : N/A
Virtual DNN sel : -
Virtual DNN sel user-range type : -
Virtual DNN sel scope : N/A
Auth Status : IMSI authenticated
PEI        : 2062180100001000
GPSI      : 12345
RAT        : NR
Interworking : Not Subscribed
Data Session Id : 0x00382120
SMF type    : SMF
Ref-point/Sig-pr: N11/http2      APN restriction : 0
5G Capability
  RQI      : Disabled      Multihoming : Disabled
PDU Session ID : 5
PCRF Subscribed PRAs
OCs Subscribed PRAs
UL APN AMBR : 1000.00 Mbps    DL APN AMBR : 1000.00 Mbps
Bearer contexts : 2          SDFs : 2

Primary DNS IPv4 address : -
Secondary DNS IPv4 address : -
Primary DNS IPv6 address : -
Secondary DNS IPv6 address : -

Pri NBNS IPv4 ad*: -      Sec NBNS IPv4 ad*: -
Pri NBNS IPv6 ad*: -
Sec NBNS IPv6 ad*: -

Charging bearer *: Visiting
UE IPv4 address : 100.64.15.0
UE IPv4 address source : Local Pool

Charging profile : 0      Interim records *: 0
RF triggers : 0

Framed Routes : 0

P-CSCF Reselection : Y

Override Rating Group : N/A
Override Online Billing Method : Disabled
Override Offline Billing Method : Disabled
MO Exception Cou*: 0      MO Exception Tim*: 0

ULI Timestmp(sec): 0      SSC Mode : 1
N3 State : Active
LADN state : Inactive

NSSAI
SST : 1      SD : 0x000002
```

Figure 13: Example of 5G SA SIM attached on network slice S-NSSAI-2 via 5G SA RAN.

As mentioned above, within S-NSSAI-1/2/3 there are default 5QI and dedicated 5QI. An example of a 5G UE on S-NSSAI-2 with two QoS flows activated is shown below:

```
A:AN0990-CMU-SMF01# show mobile-gateway pdn pdn-context
=====
IMSI/IMEI( #)      APN      Type  Beare* UE Address (IPv4/IPv6)  Ref-pt/Si*
/MSISDN(^)/MAC(^)
/SubId/SEID(~)
-----
206059899018004  live-str* IPv4  2      100.64.15.0/-                  N11/http2
-----
Number of PDN instances : 1
-----
# indicates that the corresponding row is IMEI entry.
^ indicates that the corresponding row is MSISDN entry.
\ indicates that the corresponding row is MAC entry.
~ indicates that the corresponding row is SEID entry.
-----
* indicates that the corresponding row element may have been truncated.
A:AN0990-CMU-SMF01#
A:AN0990-CMU-SMF01# show mobile-gateway pdn qos-flow
=====
SUPI/PEI( #)      DNN      QFI  Type  5QI/ARP  MBR/GBR  SDFs
/GPSI(^)/MAC(^)
/SubId/SEID(~)
-----
206059899018004  live-stream  1    Def  8/15    ~        1
206059899018004  live-stream  3    GBR  4/9     5000000/500* 1
-----
Number of QFIs : 2
-----
# indicates that the corresponding row is IMEI entry.
^ indicates that the corresponding row is MSISDN entry.
\ indicates that the corresponding row is MAC entry.
~ indicates that the corresponding row is SEID entry.
-----
* indicates that the corresponding row element may have been truncated.
```

Figure 14: Example of 5G SA SIM on S-NSSAI-2 with two 5QI flows.

5.1.1.3. Integration validation test results

The test was conducted in one of the sites north of Port of Antwerp. During the test 3 locations on the road side were selected, together with two locations on the waterway. Note that the test environment was using 50MHz of 3.5GHz spectrum instead of 100MHz.

Land location 1:

The first location is 350 metres away from the gNB with good signal strength of -64dBm RSRP and 23dB SINR. This reflects a good coverage scenario with a clear line of sight. The 5G UE is configured to connect to the eMBB slice.

Figure 15: Land location 1 TCP UL single UE speed eMBB throughput.

As shown in the figure above, the average TCP UL bandwidth is 29.7Mbps with standard deviation of 3.015942397585799. Note that the drop of speed is caused by trucks passing by.

Figure 16: Land location 1 TCP DL single UE speed eMBB throughput.

As shown in figure above, the average TCP DL bandwidth is 409 Mbps with standard deviation 41.45246924557757. Note that the drop of speed is caused by trucks passing by.

Figure 17: Land location 1 latency test without load eMBB throughput.

The latency is measured by performing ping tests without extra load on the default slice. The result is shown in the figure above, i.e., average latency of 22ms, with 14ms minimum and 40ms maximum values.

Figure 18: Land location 1 latency test with load.

The comparison latency test was performed with maximum network load on the default slice. When performing ping tests on the eMBB slice the result is as shown in the Figure 18. There is a small impact on the latency, resulting in average 24ms, minimum 19ms and maximum 45ms.

Land location 2:

The second location is 2km away from the gNB. At this location the gNB is no longer in line of sight but there are minimal obstacles on the path. The signal strength is -83dBm RSRP and 19dB SINR. This reflects a medium coverage scenario which is far from gNB but with a good radio propagation path.

Figure 19: Land location 2 TCP UL single UE speed.

As shown in figure above, the average TCP UL bandwidth is 20.7Mbps with standard deviation of 2.8206723193829752. Note that the drop of speed is caused by trucks passing by.

Figure 20: Land location 2 TCP DL single UE speed.

As shown in figure above, the average TCP DL bandwidth is 188 Mbps with standard deviation of 42.59. It should be noted that the MIMO and modulation is becoming fragile after SINR drop and the speed was unable to recover.

Land location 3:

The third location is also 2km away from the gNB but in the other direction. The test location is surrounded by high metal structures from factories nearby, a small industrial train station and high voltage lines. The signal strength is -99dBm RSRP and 7dB SINR. This reflects a far edge scenario.

Figure 21: Land location 3 TCP DL single UE speed eMBB throughput.

As shown in figure above, the average TCP DL bandwidth is 57.1 Mbps with standard deviation of 12.860326821302662. Note the MIMO and modulation is becoming fragile that after SINR drop the speed was unable to recover.

Figure 22: Land location 3 TCP UL single UE speed eMBB throughput.

As shown in figure above, the average TCP UL bandwidth is 576 Kbps with standard deviation of 0.15. Note that even though the DL speed is still acceptable, the UL speed has already dropped to its minimum value. If the UE continues to move further away from the gNB, the DL speed will continue dropping until 4.5km distance and the UE detaches. This shows that the coverage limitation for 5G SA on 3.5GHz is strongly limited by UL signal strength, much more than other technologies. Thus, when simulating network performance, simply RSRP and SINR data from 5G UE is not sufficient for 5G applications. Data from the 5G network side is required.

On waterway location 1:

The first location on water is next to the docking area on the north edge of Port of Antwerp. The location is 2.5km away from gNB on open water. The signal strength is -93dBm RSRP and 18dB SINR. Note that the SINR is better on open water compared with on land location with equivalent RSRP.

The average TCP DL speed is 259Mbps with standard deviation of 52.28. The average TCP UL speed is 24.2Mbps with standard deviation 8.13. Note that the speed drop caused by large vessels passing by and the impact is higher than trucks’ due to the size and speed of vessels.

Figure 23: Waterway location 1 TCP DL single UE speed eMBB throughput.

On waterway location 2:

The second location on water is within the north lock of Port of Antwerp. The average passing time for vessels from one side of the lock to another is 3 hours. During this time the vessel's operation needs to be uninterrupted. The location is 700m away from gNB. The water level is around 10m below land surface. All vessels are ideally in close distance with each other, including large container ships. The signal strength is -85dBm RSRP and 22dB SINR.

The average TCP DL speed is 301Mbps, while the average TCP UL speed is reduced to 8.7Mbps. This is caused by the surrounding large container ships absorbing much of UE UL signals. For the DL the signal power is sufficient as the lock is close to the gNB and beamforming can counter the effect of lower water level below ground surface. This proves again that for 5G applications, the data from 5G network is critical for estimating network performance.

Figure 24: Waterway location 2 TCP DL single UE speed eMBB throughput.

5.1.2. Management and Orchestration and Virtualized Infrastructure

Besides the 5G RAN and Core elements from the Belgian 5G testbed, we deliver a dedicated NFV infrastructure for deploying i) containerized (Docker) and VM-based Network Apps, ii) local monitoring system that interfaces and interacts with the centralized monitoring platform, and iii) slice plugin that interacts with the slice inventory component on the VITAL-5G platform. The overall architecture of the Belgian testbed could be seen in Figure 25, while all of the components are further shown on the map of the Port of Antwerp area in Figure 26. In particular,

Figure 26 showcases the location of the Network App platform running on the 5G edge, deploying the Network Apps that are accessible and used by the vessel sailing in the testing area (Port of Antwerp).

The NFV infrastructure is entirely managed and orchestrated by Open Source MANO (OSM) version 12...The previous OSM version 10 is also available and used as a backup. The entire NFV infrastructure with all the above-mentioned software components is deployed and running as a Network App platform, which is considered as a 5G edge network directly connected with the Telenet 5G network. The 5G edge network is deployed using IMEC NFV infrastructure that is now fully completed and collocated with a Telenet network aggregation point.

Concerning the management and orchestration, the OSM running on top of the Network App platform is deployed and working as an NFVO orchestrator, keeping the whole platform compliant with the design of the standardized ETSI NFV MEC framework. Network Apps are managed and orchestrated by the NFVO while using virtualized infrastructure resources managed by OpenStack and/or Kubernetes (both available). Kubernetes is an open-source system for automating deployment, scaling, and management of containerized applications.

Figure 25: The end-to-end architecture of the Belgian 5G testbed.

Figure 26: The overview of the Antwerp pilot site deployment.

5.2. Romanian Testbed

The 5G RAN and Core integration status in VITAL-5G Romanian testbed (following the target 3GPP Rel.16), as detailed in D3.1 [5], is highlighted in Table 10:

Table 10: Romanian Testbed 5G SA network status.

Type	Description	Completion Status	Version	Features
Virtualized Infrastructure IaaS/CaaS	OpenStack USSURI K8S 48TB Shared Storage 320vCPU 3TB RAM HPE DL360 GEN10	100%	USSURI K8s 2.3.x dockerv20	High Availability
Orchestration	OSM	100%	v12	High Availability
5G RAN	5G SA gNB 5G OAI	100%	SRAN18	3GPP Rel.16 High

				Availability
5G CORE	5G Core NOKIA	100%	5GSA CMU21	3GPP Rel.16 High Availability
5G Network Transport	Cisco High broadband connectivity	100%	IOS XR IP FABRIC	IP FABRIC High Availability
5G SA validated devices	Huawei PRO2 Motorola UE Huawei P40 PRO XIAOMI 12 PRO Cradlepoint R1900 Siemens MUM856 Quectel RM500Q-GL Inhand ER805 Nokia FastMile 5G (<i>multi-slice capable</i>)	100%	SA option 2	N/A
5G network monitoring	Network KPI Collection	100%	ORO 5G Probes	Internal
5G network slicing	5G SA network E2E Network slicing(3GPP)	100%	eMBB Slice URLLC Slice Multi-slice/same subscriber	SST=1 SST=2 Combined SST1&SST2

All the Romanian 5G testbed's components are deployed and integrated. For sake of security some specific related network information will be hidden by Orange in the presented outputs.

5.2.1. 5G RAN and 5G Core integration and testing, 5G Slicing Testing

In Romania Testbed the 5G SA network is deployed and integrated in the targeted release, providing 5G coverage in (1) Galati with two 5G sectors (cells) that cover Navrom ships located in the port and (2) ORO 5G Lab in Bucharest for different experiments, tests and 3rd party experiments intended to be onboarded. For clarity, only specific sets of relevant outputs will be used as validation of integration, by successfully demonstrating the 5G services availability and slice and multi-slice services (eMBB and URLLC) availability and communication.

5G SA Integrated components are based on the elements presented in next Figure 27:

Figure 27: Romanian testbed 5G SA components.

The 5G RAN and 5G Core integration and testing, including the 5G slicing testing, is based on the next validation topology architecture, where multi-devices are being connected for E2E integration testing support, as DNN1 is configured as the eMBB service slice and DNN2 is configured as URLLC service slice. E2E tests are performed using 5G Devices and test servers, highlighted in blue and red in Figure 28.

Figure 28: Romanian testbed 5G SA component service flow.

5.2.1.1. RAN Integration and Core integration

The following output is demonstrating the integration and validation of Galati 5G RAN - 5G Core in 5G SA mode.

```

GA0039_NR
+++ GA0039_NR 2022-11-28 16:05:38
O&M #8775
%%/*1879945967*/DSP SCTPLNK:;%%
RETCODE = 0 Operation succeeded.

Display SCTP Link Status
-----
Link No. = 70000
Deployment Cabinet No. = 0
Deployment Subrack No. = 0
Deployment Slot No. = 7
VRF Index = 0
IP Version = IPv4
First Local IP Address = 10.233.135.2
Second Local IP Address = 0.0.0.0
First Local IPv6 Address = NULL
Second Local IPv6 Address = NULL
Local SCTP Port No. = XXXXX
First Peer IP Address = 172.28.22.82
Second Peer IP Address = 0.0.0.0
First Peer IPv6 Address = NULL
Second Peer IPv6 Address = NULL
Peer SCTP Port No. = XXXXX
DSCP = 46
Out Stream Number = 2
In Stream Number = 2
Work Address Flag = Active Path
Working Local IP Address = 10.233.135.2
Working Peer IP Address = 172.28.22.82
Block Flag = Unblock
SCTP Link Status = Up
DTLS Link Status = Disable
Status Change Cause = Normal
Status Change Time = 2022-11-23 16:32:57
Maximum SCTP PDU Size(byte) = 1464
(Number of results = 1)
    
```

Figure 29: Romanian testbed 5G SA gNB - 5G SA core association at gNB level.

```

[cmm@cmu-necc0 ~]$ cmm nbiPing list --pingTarget 10.233.135.2 --pingSourceIp 172.28.22.82
+-----+-----+
| nbiPing | pingOutput |
+-----+-----+
| 10.233.135.2~0 | PING 10.233.135.2 (10.233.135.2) from 172.28.22.82 : 56(84) bytes of data. |
| 10.233.135.2~1 | 64 bytes from 10.233.135.2: icmp_seq=1 ttl=249 time=6.23 ms |
| 10.233.135.2~2 | 64 bytes from 10.233.135.2: icmp_seq=2 ttl=249 time=6.25 ms |
| 10.233.135.2~3 | 64 bytes from 10.233.135.2: icmp_seq=3 ttl=249 time=6.29 ms |
| 10.233.135.2~4 | 64 bytes from 10.233.135.2: icmp_seq=4 ttl=249 time=6.41 ms |
| 10.233.135.2~5 | 64 bytes from 10.233.135.2: icmp_seq=5 ttl=249 time=6.26 ms |
| 10.233.135.2~6 | |
| 10.233.135.2~7 | --- 10.233.135.2 ping statistics --- |
| 10.233.135.2~8 | 5 packets transmitted, 5 received, 0% packet loss, time 6ms |
| 10.233.135.2~9 | rtt min/avg/max/mdev = 6.232/6.288/6.412/0.086 ms |
+-----+-----+
    
```

Figure 30: Romanian testbed 5G SA gNB Galati - 5G SA core connectivity.

Figure 30 presents the 5G SA gNB communication with the 5GCN, testing the connectivity from the 5GCN to the gNB, validating also the Transport path, while Figure 31 is demonstrating the 5G SA slicing gNB level configuration.

```
GA0039_NR
+++ GA0039_NR 2022-11-22 10:37:26
O&M #2685439262
%%/*1890071175*/LST GNBTRANS:;%%
RETCODE = 0 Operation succeeded.

List gNodeB Tracking Area Network Slice
-----
Tracking Area ID Operator ID Slice Service Type Slice Differentiator Network Slice State
-----
0 0 1 11259375 Unlocked
0 0 2 11259370 Unlocked
(Number of results = 2)
```

Figure 31: Romanian testbed 5G SA slicing gNB configuration.

Figure 32 is demonstrating the 5G SA slicing gNB cell activation (2 cells installed and activated in Galati).

```
GA0039_NR
+++ GA0039_NR 2022-11-22 10:49:35
O&M #2685439274
%%/*1890074301*/LST NRCELLNS:;%%
RETCODE = 0 Operation succeeded.

List NR Cell Network Slice Information
-----
NR Cell ID Operator ID Slice Service Type Slice Differentiator Network Slice State
-----
1 0 1 11259375 Unlocked
1 0 2 11259370 Unlocked
2 0 1 11259375 Unlocked
2 0 2 11259370 Unlocked
(Number of results = 4)
```

Figure 32: Romanian testbed 5G SA slicing gNB cell activation.

```
[cmm@cmu-necc0 ~]$ cmm snssai show eMBB
+-----+
| Field          | Value  |
+-----+
| snssai         | eMBB  |
| name*         | eMBB  |
| sliceServiceType | 1     |
| sliceDifferentiator | ABCDEF |
| supportedInAllTa | true  |
+-----+
```

Figure 33: Romanian testbed 5G SA eMBB slicing configuration Core AMF.

Figure 33 and Figure 34 are demonstrating the 5G SA slicing configuration Core AMF.

```
[cmm@cmu-necc0 ~]$ cmm snssai show URLLC
+-----+-----+
| Field          | Value  |
+-----+-----+
| snssai         | URLLC  |
| name*          | URLLC  |
| sliceServiceType | 2      |
| sliceDifferentiator | ABCDEA |
| supportedInAllTa | true   |
+-----+-----+
```

Figure 34: Romanian testbed 5G SA URLLC slicing configuration Core AMF.

```
oro-5g-upf01# show mobile-gateway profile list slice-list
=====
Network Slice List(s)
=====
Slice List          : slicelist1
-----
Slice Name          : NSSAI-1
  Slice Service Type : 1
  Suspended          : No
  Slice Differentiator : 0xabcd
  Slice Instances    : -
Slice Name          : NSSAI-2
  Slice Service Type : 2
  Suspended          : No
  Slice Differentiator : 0xabcd
  Slice Instances    : -
Number of Slices    : 2
=====
```

Figure 35: Romanian testbed 5G SA slicing configuration details Core UPF.

Figure 35 is presenting 5G SA slicing configuration for 5GCN at the UPF level.

We have demonstrated, based on the 5G SA Network components listed in Table 10, that the 5G network components are deployed and integrated (RAN, Core and Transport), as targeted, by implementing all the software and hardware upgrades required, as described in D3.1 [5], validating also the E2E slice configuration and availability for two network slices.

```
[cmm@cmu-necc0 ~]$ cmm snssaiToDnn list
+-----+
| snssaiToDnn |
+-----+
| DNN1~eMBB   |
| DNN2~URLLC  |
| DNN3~eMBB   |
+-----+
[cmm@cmu-necc0 ~]$ cmm snssaiToDnn show DNN1~eMBB
+-----+-----+
| Field          | Value          |
+-----+-----+
| snssaiToDnn    | DNN1~eMBB     |
| snssaiToDnnListName* | DNN1         |
| snssaiName*    | eMBB          |
| dataNetworkName | orange5glab   |
+-----+-----+
[cmm@cmu-necc0 ~]$ cmm snssaiToDnn show DNN2~URLLC
+-----+-----+
| Field          | Value          |
+-----+-----+
| snssaiToDnn    | DNN2~URLLC    |
| snssaiToDnnListName* | DNN2         |
| snssaiName*    | URLLC         |
| dataNetworkName | orangeurllc   |
+-----+-----+
```

Figure 36: Romanian test-bed 5G SA DNN/NSSAI slicing details.

Figure 36 is presenting 5G SA the DNN and NSSAI for slicing at Core level, the DNN1 for eMBB and the DNN2 for URLLC. We present a clear slicing definition and implementation, in line with 3GPP.

For the integration and validation slice use-case, slices are configured, with different NSSAI and slice differentiators (SD), configuring and implementing different slices profiles, as detailed in Figure 37.

```
{
  "name": "eMBB2",
  "am": {
    "gpsis": [
      "msisdn-12345"
    ],
    "subscribedUeAmbr": {
      "uplink": "2000 Mbps",
      "downlink": "2000 Mbps"
    },
    "nssai": {
      "defaultSingleNssais": [
        {
          "sst": 1,
          "sd": "ABCDEF"
        }
      ]
    },
    "subscribedDnnList": [
      "orange5glab"
    ]
  },
},
{
  "name": "URLLC-40M",
  "am": {
    "gpsis": [
      "msisdn-12346"
    ],
    "subscribedUeAmbr": {
      "uplink": "40 Mbps",
      "downlink": "40 Mbps"
    },
    "nssai": {
      "defaultSingleNssais": [
        {
          "sst": 2,
          "sd": "ABCDEA"
        }
      ]
    },
    "subscribedDnnList": [
      "orangeurllc"
    ]
  },
},
```

Figure 37: Romanian testbed 5G SA profiles slice configuration.

We configure different series of IMSI/Subscribers that are connected to the slices, for different user requirements and capabilities (eMBB or URLLC), as presented in Figure 38.

```
oro-5g-upf01>config>mobile>pdn# show mobile-gateway pdn pdu-session
=====
SUPI/PEI( #)      DNN      Type    QFIs    PDU Address (IPv4/IPv6) Ref-pt/Si*
/GPSI(^)/MAC(`)
/SubId/SEID(~)
=====
0x19e0130~        orangeur* IPv4     1       10.87.69.65/-          N/A
  226107900000071
0x1b70130~        orange5g* IPv4     1       10.87.69.2/-          N/A
  226107900000007
0x1ba0130~        orange5g* IPv4     1       10.87.69.8/-          N/A
  226107900000072
0x2120130~        orange5g* IPv4     1       10.87.69.42/-         N/A
  226107900000006
0x2130130~        orange5g* IPv4     1       10.87.69.31/-         N/A
  226107900000005
=====
Number of PDU sessions : 5
```

Figure 38: Romanian testbed 5G SA subscribers attached to the slices.

We performed validation of a 5G SA subscriber (attached to one slice) connected to the 5G SA network, for eMBB slice, as seen in Figure 39:

```
oro-5g-upf01# show mobile-gateway pdn pdu-session supi 226107900000072 detail
=====
PDU session detail
=====
IMSI           : 226107900000072
Gi Network Inst : orange5glab
PDN Type       : IPv4
UL APN AMBR    : 2000.00 Mbps      DL APN AMBR    : 2000.00 Mbps
Bearer contexts : 1              GW/Group/VM    : 1/1/3
UE IPv4 Address : 10.87.69.8
CP Sx-N4 Seid  : 0xa90100         UP Sx-N4 Seid  : 0x1ba0130
CP Sx-N4 Ctl V4 *: 172.28.22.126  UP Sx-N4 Ctl V4 *: 172.28.22.65
PDRs           : 2              FARS           : 2
QERs           : 2
BAR ID         : 5
State          : CONNECTED      AA Session Id   : 0x0004clba
Def PFCP-u Sess : False
Network/Itf Realm: N/A
DL APN rate lmt Drp Pkt : 0
UL APN rate lmt Drp Pkt : 0
PLMN rate lmt Drp Pkt   : 0
L2TP Connection ID      : 0

NSSAI
SST           : 1              SD              : 0xab0def
=====
```

Figure 39: Romanian testbed 5G SA subscriber eMBB slice characteristics.

```

oro-5g-upf01# show mobile-gateway pdn pdu-session
=====
SUPI/PEI(##)      DNN      Type    QFIs    PDU Address (IPv4/IPv6) Ref-pt/Si*
/GPSI(^)/MAC(`)
/SubId/SEID(~)
=====
0x3b0120~         orangeur* IPv4    1       10.87.69.128/-        N/A
226107900000086

oro-5g-upf01# show mobile-gateway pdn pdu-session supi 226107900000086 detail
=====
PDU session detail
=====
IMSI              : 226107900000086
Gi Network Inst   : orangeurllc
PDN Type          : IPv4
UL APN AMBR       : 40.00 Mbps          DL APN AMBR       : 40.00 Mbps
Bearer contexts   : 1              GW/Group/VM      : 1/1/3
UE IPv4 Address   : 10.87.69.128
CP Sx-N4 Seid     : 0x2910130          UP Sx-N4 Seid     : 0x3b0120
CP Sx-N4 Ctl V4  *: 172.28.22.126  UP Sx-N4 Ctl V4  *: 172.28.22.65
PDRs              : 2              FARS              : 2
QERs              : 2
BAR ID           : 5
State             : CONNECTED          AA Session Id     : 0x0004803b
Def PFCP-u Sess   : False
Network/Itf Realm: N/A
DL APN rate lmt Drp Pkt : 0
UL APN rate lmt Drp Pkt : 0
PLMN rate lmt Drp Pkt  : 0
L2TP Connection ID  : 0

NSSAI
SST              : 2              SD                : 0xab0cdea
=====
Number of PDN contexts : 1
    
```

Figure 40: Romanian testbed 5G SA subscriber URLLC slice characteristics.

We demonstrate an active data session for the 5G SA network. The PDN session is in connected mode and has one dedicated bearer, validating the proper network attachment.

The 5G SA subscribers are authenticated, registered and connected to the 5G SA network, demonstrating the proper UDM and AUSF functionality, as described in Figure 41.

```

[cmm@cmu-necc0 ~]$ cmm subscriber show --imsi 226107900000072 | grep State
|                                     | amfCmState: CONNECTED
|                                     | amfRmState: REGISTERED
|                                     | dumpCxnStateTrans: 0
|                                     | cmConnectedState: NG SXN ESTAB
|                                     | upCnxState: state activated
    
```

Figure 41: Romanian testbed 5G SA subscriber Registered and Connected State.

As a conclusion, the Romanian testbed is fully 5G SA integrated, as validated based on the presented relevant outputs from the network. The end-to-end slices performance is validated by running experiments and network tests, using a subscriber connected to one of the slices (e.g., eMBB slice for E2E throughput validation or URLLC for E2E latency validation), as we present the relevant output from the slice and service functionality for one of the declared subscribers in the system.

We perform an E2E 5G SA network validation of the testbed, by running different experiments, to demonstrate eMBB slice throughput characteristics and URLLC latency characteristics, as seen in Figure 42 and Figure 43, the real field results are confirming the 5G SA KPIs in terms of network, as DL/UL throughput (600Mbps DL, 100Mbps UL) and latency (<3.5ms one way delay).

```
DL: iperf3.exe -c 172.28.16.27 -p 5001 -b 200Mbps -P 8 -l 1310 -t 86400 -R
[ 4]  4.00-5.00  sec  9.54 MBytes  80.0 Mbits/sec
[ 6]  4.00-5.00  sec  9.98 MBytes  83.7 Mbits/sec
[ 8]  4.00-5.00  sec  9.82 MBytes  82.4 Mbits/sec
[10]  4.00-5.00  sec  9.90 MBytes  83.1 Mbits/sec
[12]  4.00-5.00  sec  9.70 MBytes  81.4 Mbits/sec
[14]  4.00-5.00  sec  9.81 MBytes  82.3 Mbits/sec
[16]  4.00-5.00  sec 10.1 MBytes  85.0 Mbits/sec
[18]  4.00-5.00  sec  9.86 MBytes  82.7 Mbits/sec
[SUM] 4.00-5.00  sec  78.8 MBytes  661 Mbits/sec
-----
UL: iperf3.exe -c 172.28.16.27 -p 5001 -b 50Mbps -P 8 -l 1310 -t 86400
[ 4]  3.00-4.00  sec  1.54 MBytes  12.9 Mbits/sec
[ 6]  3.00-4.00  sec  1.55 MBytes  13.0 Mbits/sec
[ 8]  3.00-4.00  sec  1.55 MBytes  13.0 Mbits/sec
[10]  3.00-4.00  sec  1.52 MBytes  12.7 Mbits/sec
[12]  3.00-4.00  sec  1.54 MBytes  12.9 Mbits/sec
[14]  3.00-4.00  sec  1.50 MBytes  12.6 Mbits/sec
[16]  3.00-4.00  sec  1.52 MBytes  12.8 Mbits/sec
[18]  3.00-4.00  sec  1.55 MBytes  13.0 Mbits/sec
[SUM] 3.00-4.00  sec  12.3 MBytes  103 Mbits/sec
-----
```

Figure 42: Romanian testbed 5G SA eMBB test results (UL/DL) - iperf3.

```
iperf3-server:~$ ping 10.87.69.65
PING 10.87.69.50 (10.87.69.50) 56(84) bytes of data.
64 bytes from 10.87.69.50: icmp_seq=1 ttl=60 time=6.08 ms
64 bytes from 10.87.69.50: icmp_seq=2 ttl=60 time=5.81 ms
64 bytes from 10.87.69.50: icmp_seq=3 ttl=60 time=5.82 ms
64 bytes from 10.87.69.50: icmp_seq=4 ttl=60 time=6.81 ms
64 bytes from 10.87.69.50: icmp_seq=5 ttl=60 time=6.79 ms
64 bytes from 10.87.69.50: icmp_seq=6 ttl=60 time=7.88 ms
64 bytes from 10.87.69.50: icmp_seq=7 ttl=60 time=8.84 ms
rtt min/avg/max/mdev = 4.791/6.861/8.088/1.449 ms
```

Figure 43: Romanian testbed 5G SA URLLC test results(latency) - iperf3.

We have implemented as a novelty and key VITAL-5G output in industry the 5G SA multi-slice implementation for a single subscriber, by using an advanced 5G SA Nokia CPE, as in Figure 45. We have defined a specific E2E Network Slice in Galati and attached through the Slice Management Interface a subscriber in the multi-slice context, PDPs contexts active in the same time for eMBB and URLLC, as seen in Figure 44 below:

```
oro-5g-upf01# show mobile-gateway pdn bearer-context supi 226107900000077 detail |
Gi Network Inst : orangeurllc
N3 DL packets   : 912839           N3 DL bytes      : 1212749520
SGI UL packets  : 143092           SGI UL bytes     : 6308403
Gi Network Inst : orange5glab
N3 DL packets   : 1556773          N3 DL bytes      : 2105226110
SGI UL packets  : 1499362          SGI UL bytes     : 565748002
```

Figure 44: PDPs contexts active in the same time for eMBB and URLLC.

Network / Cellular / APN - Access Point Name

orangeurllc		orange5glab	
Default Connected		Connected	
Work Mode	RouteMode	Work Mode	BridgeMode
Service	TR069,INTERNET	Service	DATA
Interface	Ethernet 1, VLAN ID 100	Interface	Ethernet 1, VLAN ID 200
Authentication Mode	None	Authentication Mode	None
IPv4	10.87.69.139	IPv4	10.87.69.13
IPv4 Netmask	Automatic	IPv4 Netmask	Automatic
IPv6	Not Available	IPv6	Not Available
MTU	1400	MTU	1400

Figure 45: Multi-slice implementation for a single subscriber, by using an advanced 5G SA Nokia CPE.

We have performed a series of tests for network validation and integration, high-availability of 5G services, including tests in the LAB environment, and experimenting with 5G SA functionality with no 5G SA network issues for several months (more than 4 months, with at least one user permanently connected to the 5G SA network and generating traffic), as it can be seen in Figure 46.

```
[cmm@cmu-necc0 ~]$ uptime
18:51:39 up 160 days, 7:10, 1 user, load average: 0.69, 0.46, 0.44

oro-5g-upf01# show uptime
System Up Time      : 160 days, 07:10:48.01 (hr:min:sec)
```

Figure 46: Romanian testbed 5G SA network availability.

We have performed several extensive throughput tests, collecting the relevant metrics and KPIs, validating also the UL/DL data collection, at different levels, as seen in Figure 47 and Figure 48:

Figure 47: Romanian testbed 5G SA eMBB extensive test results (DL) - gNB level.

Figure 48: Romanian testbed 5G SA eMBB extensive test results (UL) - gNB level.

5.2.2. Management and Orchestration and Virtualized Infrastructure

Romanian testbed orchestrator is based on OSMv12, deployed in the infrastructure and integrated with both VITAL-5G platform LCM component and the testbed VIM, by using Openstack solution, in a High-Availability mode and Kubernetes cluster. Details about the technical architecture and implementation of the target solution for Orchestration and Virtualization are presented in D3.1 [5].

Table 11: VITAL-5G Management and Orchestration testbed status.

M&O Testbed Components	Integration status with VITAL-5G Platform Components	Integration status with OSM	Comments
VITAL-5G Platform LCM	--	100%	See deployments and onboarding Sprints
OSM	100% SOL006	--	
Openstack VIM	--	100% SOL005	See Network Apps VM deployments during sprints
Kubernetes	--	100%	The K8s cluster is integrated with OMSv12, ready for CNFs deployments

Romanian testbed components availability, deployment and integration are demonstrated and validated during the presented sprints and highlighted further based on the next relevant outputs.

Figure 49 is demonstrating the OSM deployment in ORO Testbed, including NS packages and VNF packages availability.

Figure 49: Romanian testbed OSM deployment.

The OSM is connected to the Openstack VIM infrastructure, for VNFs services onboarding and deployments. Table 12 is demonstrating the logic connectivity to the VIM:

Table 12: Romanian testbed OSM VIM Openstack.

Name	Identifier	Type
openstack_5glab_vim	5d916341-a283-4781-80cf-1e92d318f6b8	openstack

Figure 50: Romanian testbed OSM VIM integration.

The OSM and orchestration capabilities are available for deployments, as demonstrated in Figure 51, as a VNF instance is deployed through orchestration and instantiated in the Openstack cluster.

Figure 51: Romanian testbed OSM NS instance.

The VNF instance deployment through OSM is functionally validated, as shown in the Openstack cluster represented in Figure 52.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Instance Name	Image Name	IP Address	Flavor	Key Pair	Status	Availability Zone	Task	Power State
<input type="checkbox"/>	oro_vnf-1-ubuntu-VM-0	Ubuntu-18.04	192.168.32.192	cirros-VM-flv	-	Active	nova	None	Running

Figure 52: Romanian testbed VMs deployment through OSM.

For proper demonstration of Orchestration and Virtualization integration in the ecosystem, we have deployed for test purposes a VM through OSM that can be retrieved in Openstack, as in Table 13:

Table 13: Romanian testbed infrastructure VMs deployment.

Overview	Instance Console Log
Name oro_vnf-1-ubuntu-VM-0 ID e087e9bf-cd6e-4195-a166-949b3c02e47d Description oro_vnf-1-ubuntu-VM-0 Project ID ba3b97ef1dc24996a85fe29533e94b26 Status Active Locked False Availability Zone nova Created 39 minutes Host 5glab-node06	<pre> [[0;32m OK [0m] Created slice system-getty.slice. [[0;32m OK [0m] Started Getty on tty1. [[0;32m OK [0m] Reached target Login Prompts. [[0;32m OK [0m] Started Authorization Manager. [[0;32m OK [0m] Started Accounts Service. [[0;32m OK [0m] Started LSB: automatic crash report generation. [[0;32m OK [0m] Started LSB: Record successful boot for GRUB. [[0;32m OK [0m] Started Hostname Service. [[0;32m OK [0m] Started LXDM - container startup/shutdown. [[0;32m OK [0m] Started Dispatcher daemon for systemd-networkd. [[0;32m OK [0m] Started Snap Daemon. Starting Wait until snapd is fully seeded... Starting Time & Date Service... [[0;32m OK [0m] Started Time & Date Service. </pre>

We have deployed and integrated an HA virtualized infrastructure, described in D3.1 for Romanian testbed, for Network Apps developers and 3rd parties, an Openstack cluster, physically deployed as a hypervisors deployment and logically implemented as shown in Figure 53.

Host	Availability zone	Status	State
5glab-node06	nova	Enabled	Up
5glab-node05	nova	Enabled	Up
5glab-node04	nova	Enabled	Up

Figure 53: Romanian testbed IaaS computes nodes.

In the Romanian testbed, there have been defined a large series of Images and Flavours to be adequately used by the developers and infrastructure users, i.e., Images and Flavours that can be adapted to cope with any end-user requirements, as shown in Figure 54 and Figure 55.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Flavor Name	VCPUs	RAM	Root Disk	Ephemeral Disk	Swap Disk	RX/TX factor	ID	Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	m1.large	4	8GB	80GB	0GB	0MB	1.0	4	Yes
<input type="checkbox"/>	m1.medium	2	4GB	40GB	0GB	0MB	1.0	3	Yes
<input type="checkbox"/>	m1.small	1	2GB	20GB	0GB	0MB	1.0	2	Yes
<input type="checkbox"/>	m1.tiny	1	512MB	1GB	0GB	0MB	1.0	1	Yes
<input type="checkbox"/>	m1.xlarge	8	16GB	160GB	0GB	0MB	1.0	5	Yes

Figure 54: Romanian testbed flavours availability in Openstack.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Project	Host	Name	Image Name	IP Address	Flavor	Status	Task	Power State
<input type="checkbox"/>	admin	5glab-node05	test-snap-cirros	cirros	10.0.0.85	m1.tiny	Active	None	Running
<input type="checkbox"/>	admin	5glab-node05	ubuntu-test	Ubuntu-18.04	provider-1 demo-net	m1.medium	Active	None	Running
<input type="checkbox"/>	admin	5glab-node06	centos-test	CentOS-8-GenericCloud-8.4	demo-net 1 provider-v1	m1.medium	Active	None	Running

Figure 55: Romanian testbed images availability in Openstack.

The Romanian testbed has also implemented an advanced monitoring system of the 5G network, virtualized environment and Network Apps, as described in D3.1 [5] for Romanian Cluster, examples of the Prometheus output in the Figure 56.

5glab-node03 (1/1 up) [show less](#)

Endpoint	State	Labels	Last Scrape	Scrape Duration
http://172.28.16.13:9966/metrics	UP	instance="172.28.16.13:9966" job="5glab-node03"	3.09s ago	72.21ms

big_data_vm (1/1 up) [show less](#)

Endpoint	State	Labels	Last Scrape	Scrape Duration
http://172.28.22.189:9100/metrics	UP	instance="172.28.22.189:9100" job="big_data_vm"	13.798s ago	42.48ms

Figure 56: Romanian testbed Prometheus monitoring.

In conclusion, the Romanian testbed has fully implemented the 5G SA evolution path to Rel.16, with the upgrades to the targeted network implementation, including orchestration and virtualization environment deployment,

capable of automatic services and Network Apps instantiation through VITAL-5G Platform, ensuring end-to-end connectivity from the Network Applications to the 5G SA capable end-devices connected to the network.

5.3. Greek Testbed

The current status of the Greek testbed infrastructure is depicted in Table 14.

Table 14: Greek Testbed Infrastructure.

Type	Description	Completion Status (1)	Version	Features
IPSec	IPSec gateway to connect the Greek testbed with the VITAL-5G platform located in Bucharest	100%	pfSense 2.5.1	
OpenStack (for 5G Core deployment)	OpenStack cloud 352 vCPUs 576 GB RAM 4 TB storage	100%	Red Hat OpenStack Platform release 16.1.8 (Train)	High availability
5G Core SA	5G Core of the Greek testbed	100%	Athonet 3.1.3	3GPP Rel 16
5G RAN	Ericsson BB 6630 and two ERS 4408	100%		3GPP Rel 16
5G Network Transport	IP MPLS	100%	NA	High availability
5G SA validated devices	Quectel RMU500EK, Nokia Fastmile 5G Gateway, Huawei, HUAWEI 5G Mobile WiFi Pro	100%	V3.1	
5G network monitoring	Network, Service and Infrastructure KPIs	100%		Featuring a Monitoring plugin and multiple Prometheus instances.
5G network slicing	End to end network slicing available	100%		Multiple eMBRR and URLLC static network slices for Drop II.
SSOpenStack (Virtual Infrastructure for	Virtual Infrastructure Manager for	100%	v. 5.4.0 (Victoria)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Additional native integration with Kubernetes

NetApps deployment)	VNF Network Apps			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More support for diverse architectures and standards • Solutions for complex networking issues
OSM	Network App orchestrator	100%	v. 12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distributed VNF Configuration and Abstraction • Scaling for Kubernetes Applications • Improved Scale-in/Scale-out functionality • Reduced footprint and improved release process
Kubernetes	open-source system for automating deployment, scaling, and management of containerized applications	100%	v 1.24.6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automated rollouts and rollbacks • Service discovery and load balancing • Horizontal scaling • Designed for extensibility

5.3.1. 5G RAN and 5G Core integration and testing.

Figure 57 shows an overview of the infrastructure of the Greek testbed. On the right there are the Diakinisis premises with the gNodeB and the AGV and on the left, the OTE premises where all the other trial infrastructure is hosted.

The infrastructure consists of the WINGS Virtualization infrastructure, the OTE Openstack (used for the deployment of the 5G CN) and management systems, such as the Ericsson EMS for managing the gNodeB.

The OTE infrastructure consists of a highly available Red Hat OpenStack Platform release 16.1.8 (Train) with 352 vCPUs, 576 GB RAM and 4TB storage. This Openstack hosts the Athonet 5G Core SA, which is a full release 16 5G Core and the Monitoring System. The latter is based on Prometheus and Grafana.

The connectivity between the trial site located at the OTE building and the VITAL-5G platform is through an IPSec tunnel. The IP MPLS network connects the gNodeB, located at Diakinisis, with the 5G Core SA, located at OTE premises.

Figure 57: Overview of the Greek Testbed Infrastructure.

Figure 58: Combined diagram of PING and MQTT latencies.

Figure 59: RTT latency for the MQTT server at the Athens testbed.

Figure 60: ICMP latency for the Athens Testbed.

Figure 61: Distribution of the ICMP latencies at the Athens testbed.

In the following console output, we can see the Bitrate from the VM located at OTE Premises to the UE connected to the 5G network at DIAKINISIS premises.

```
iperf3 -c 10.10.9.46 -p5005 -R
Connecting to host 10.10.9.46, port 5005
Reverse mode, remote host 10.10.9.46 is sending
[ 5] local 192.168.8.108 port 33454 connected to 10.10.9.46 port 5005
[ ID] Interval            Transfer          Bitrate
[ 5]  0.00-1.00      sec    17.9 MBytes    151 Mbits/sec
[ 5]  1.00-2.00      sec    20.6 MBytes    173 Mbits/sec
[ 5]  2.00-3.00      sec    22.3 MBytes    187 Mbits/sec
[ 5]  3.00-4.00      sec    23.2 MBytes    195 Mbits/sec
[ 5]  4.00-5.00      sec    18.9 MBytes    158 Mbits/sec
[ 5]  5.00-6.00      sec    16.6 MBytes    139 Mbits/sec
[ 5]  6.00-7.00      sec    16.9 MBytes    142 Mbits/sec
[ 5]  7.00-8.00      sec    17.7 MBytes    148 Mbits/sec
[ 5]  8.00-9.00      sec    18.6 MBytes    156 Mbits/sec
[ 5]  9.00-10.00     sec    19.9 MBytes    167 Mbits/sec
-----
[ ID] Interval            Transfer          Bitrate          Retr
[ 5]  0.00-10.04      sec    195 MBytes    163 Mbits/sec    55
[ 5]  0.00-10.00      sec    193 MBytes    162 Mbits/sec

sender
receiver
```

the following console output we can see the Bitrate from the UE connected to the 5G network at DIAKINISIS premises to the VM located at OTE Premises.

```
iperf3 -c 10.10.9.46 -p5005
Connecting to host 10.10.9.46, port 5005
[ 5] local 192.168.8.108 port 35052 connected to 10.10.9.46 port 5005
[ ID] Interval            Transfer          Bitrate          Retr  Cwnd
[ 5]  0.00-1.00      sec    11.1 MBytes    93.4 Mbits/sec    0    799 KBytes
[ 5]  1.00-2.00      sec    10.4 MBytes    86.9 Mbits/sec    0    1.27 MBytes
```

[5]	2.00-3.00	sec	10.0 MBytes	83.9 Mbites/sec	0	1.76 MBytes
[5]	3.00-4.00	sec	10.0 MBytes	83.9 Mbites/sec	0	2.25 MBytes
[5]	4.00-5.00	sec	10.0 MBytes	83.9 Mbites/sec	0	2.74 MBytes
[5]	5.00-6.00	sec	8.75 MBytes	73.4 Mbites/sec	0	3.17 MBytes
[5]	6.00-7.00	sec	10.0 MBytes	83.9 Mbites/sec	0	3.17 MBytes
[5]	7.00-8.00	sec	10.0 MBytes	83.9 Mbites/sec	0	3.17 MBytes
[5]	8.00-9.00	sec	8.75 MBytes	73.4 Mbites/sec	0	3.17 MBytes
[5]	9.00-10.00	sec	10.0 MBytes	83.9 Mbites/sec	0	3.17 MBytes

[ID]	Interval		Transfer	Bitrate	Retr	
[5]	0.00-10.00	sec	99.0 MBytes	83.0 Mbites/sec	0	sender
[5]	0.00-10.32	sec	98.9 MBytes	80.4 Mbites/sec		receiver

In the following console output, we can see the Bitrate from the RaspberryPi connected to the 5G network at DIAKINISIS premises to the VM located at OTE Premises.

```

pi@vital-sensor-gateway:~ $ iperf3 -c 10.10.9.46 -p 5005
Connecting to host 10.10.9.46, port 5005
[ 5] local 10.1.1.2 port 52458 connected to 10.10.9.46 port 5005
[ ID] Interval          Transfer      Bitrate      Retr  Cwnd
[ 5]  0.00-1.00      sec   9.16 MBytes  76.8 Mbites/sec   0    497 KBytes
[ 5]  1.00-2.00      sec  10.3 MBytes  86.6 Mbites/sec   0    989 KBytes
[ 5]  2.00-3.00      sec  11.2 MBytes  93.7 Mbites/sec   0    1.43 MBytes
[ 5]  3.00-4.00      sec   8.75 MBytes  73.4 Mbites/sec   0    1.51 MBytes
[ 5]  4.00-5.00      sec  10.0 MBytes  83.9 Mbites/sec   0    1.51 MBytes
[ 5]  5.00-6.00      sec  10.0 MBytes  83.9 Mbites/sec   0    1.51 MBytes
[ 5]  6.00-7.00      sec  10.0 MBytes  83.9 Mbites/sec   0    1.51 MBytes
[ 5]  7.00-8.00      sec   8.75 MBytes  73.4 Mbites/sec   0    1.51 MBytes
[ 5]  8.00-9.00      sec   8.75 MBytes  73.4 Mbites/sec   0    1.51 MBytes
[ 5]  9.00-10.00     sec   8.75 MBytes  73.4 Mbites/sec   0    1.51 MBytes
-----
[ ID] Interval          Transfer      Bitrate      Retr
[ 5]  0.00-10.00     sec  95.7 MBytes  80.2 Mbites/sec   0
[ 5]  0.00-10.11     sec  93.8 MBytes  77.8 Mbites/sec
    
```

In the following console output, we can see the Bitrate from the RaspberryPi connected to the 5G network at DIAKINISIS premises to the VM located at OTE Premises. In this case, the RaspberryPi connects to server but we are measuring the reverse traffic.

```

pi@vital-sensor-gateway:~ $ iperf3 -c 10.10.9.46 -p 5005 -R
Connecting to host 10.10.9.46, port 5005
Reverse mode, remote host 10.10.9.46 is sending
[ 5] local 10.1.1.2 port 51778 connected to 10.10.9.46 port 5005
[ ID] Interval          Transfer      Bitrate
[ 5]  0.00-1.00      sec   3.10 MBytes  26.0 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  1.00-2.00      sec   2.82 MBytes  23.7 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  2.00-3.00      sec   2.85 MBytes  23.9 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  3.00-4.00      sec   3.07 MBytes  25.8 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  4.00-5.00      sec   2.96 MBytes  24.8 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  5.00-6.00      sec   3.30 MBytes  27.7 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  6.00-7.00      sec   2.79 MBytes  23.4 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  7.00-8.00      sec   2.93 MBytes  24.5 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  8.00-9.00      sec   3.30 MBytes  27.7 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  9.00-10.00     sec   3.15 MBytes  26.4 Mbites/sec
-----
[ ID] Interval          Transfer      Bitrate      Retr
    
```

[5]	0.00-10.05	sec	30.8 MBytes	25.8 Mbites/sec	188	sender
[5]	0.00-10.00	sec	30.3 MBytes	25.4 Mbites/sec		receiver

In general, the maximum bitrate is 214Mbps peak (198Mbps on average) measuring from the server to the UE which is connected to the 5G network through a Huawei 5G router as can be seen also in the console output below.

```

iperf3 -c 10.10.9.46 -p5005 -R
Connecting to host 10.10.9.46, port 5005
Reverse mode, remote host 10.10.9.46 is sending
[ 5] local 192.168.8.108 port 58678 connected to 10.10.9.46 port 5005
[ ID] Interval          Transfer          Bitrate
[ 5]  0.00-1.00    sec   19.6 MBytes    165 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  1.00-2.00    sec   21.6 MBytes    181 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  2.00-3.00    sec   24.7 MBytes    207 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  3.00-4.00    sec   25.3 MBytes    213 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  4.00-5.00    sec   25.5 MBytes    214 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  5.00-6.00    sec   20.9 MBytes    175 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  6.00-7.00    sec   22.2 MBytes    187 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  7.00-8.00    sec   23.8 MBytes    199 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  8.00-9.00    sec   24.4 MBytes    205 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  9.00-10.00   sec   25.5 MBytes    214 Mbites/sec
- - - - -
[ ID] Interval          Transfer          Bitrate          Retr
[ 5]  0.00-10.03   sec   237 MBytes    198 Mbites/sec   191
[ 5]  0.00-10.00   sec   234 MBytes    196 Mbites/sec

```

Below we can see the bitrate between two UEs (laptop through the 5G router, Raspberry Pi) connected to the 5G network at DIAKINISIS premises.

```

iperf3 -c 10.1.1.2 -p 5201 -R
Connecting to host 10.1.1.2, port 5201
Reverse mode, remote host 10.1.1.2 is sending
[ 5] local 192.168.8.108 port 43050 connected to 10.1.1.2 port 5201
[ ID] Interval          Transfer          Bitrate
[ 5]  0.00-1.00    sec   3.54 MBytes    29.7 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  1.00-2.00    sec   8.70 MBytes    73.0 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  2.00-3.00    sec   9.61 MBytes    80.7 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  3.00-4.00    sec   9.60 MBytes    80.5 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  4.00-5.00    sec   9.55 MBytes    80.1 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  5.00-6.00    sec   9.00 MBytes    75.5 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  6.00-7.00    sec  10.3 MBytes    86.0 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  7.00-8.00    sec   9.63 MBytes    80.7 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  8.00-9.00    sec   9.55 MBytes    80.1 Mbites/sec
[ 5]  9.00-10.00   sec   9.69 MBytes    81.3 Mbites/sec
- - - - -
[ ID] Interval          Transfer          Bitrate          Retr
[ 5]  0.00-10.04   sec   92.6 MBytes    77.4 Mbites/sec    80
[ 5]  0.00-10.00   sec   89.1 MBytes    74.8 Mbites/sec

```

5.3.2. Slicing Testing

5.3.2.1. Ericsson gNodeB configuration

The gNodeB consists of the Ericsson BBU BB6630 with two Ericsson ERS4408 cells attached. The AMF configuration related to slicing can be seen in Figure 62.

```

=====
181                               GNBCUCPFunction=1,TermPointToAmf=AMF
=====
administrativeState                1 (UNLOCKED)
amfName                            amf.5gc.3gppnetwork.org
availabilityStatus                 i[0] =
defaultAmf                         true
domainName
ipv4Address1                       172.25.3.5
ipv4Address2                       0.0.0.0
ipv6Address1                       ::
ipv6Address2                       ::
operationalState                   1 (ENABLED)
operatorPLMNId                     Struct{2}
>>> 1.mcc = 202
>>> 2.mnc = 22
pLMNIdList                         t[1] =
>>> Struct[0] has 2 members:
>>> 1.mcc = 202
>>> 2.mnc = 02
pwsRestartHandling                 0 (DISABLED)
relativeCapacity                   100
sNSSAIIList                        t[2] =
>>> Struct[0] has 2 members:
>>> 1.sd = 16777215
>>> 2.sst = 1
>>> Struct[1] has 2 members:
>>> 1.sd = 16777215
>>> 2.sst = 2
servedGuamiList                   t[1] =
>>> Struct[0] has 5 members:
>>> 1.amfPointer = 1
>>> 2.amfRegionId = 1
>>> 3.amfSetId = 1
>>> 4.mcc = 202
>>> 5.mnc = 02
termPointToAmfId                   AMF
usedIpAddress                       172.25.3.5
=====

```

Figure 62: Greek Testbed gNB integration.

Below you can see part of the configuration of the cell, related to slicing, as in Figure 63.

```

=====
224                               GNBDFunction=1,NRCellIDU=N305151E1
=====
actualPdcchRachBoost
actualPdschRachBoost
actualSsbPowerBoost                0
.
.
.
sNSSAIIList                        t[2] =
>>> Struct[0] has 2 members:
>>> 1.sd = 16777215
>>> 2.sst = 1
>>> Struct[1] has 2 members:
>>> 1.sd = 16777215
>>> 2.sst = 2
.
.
.
ulScSpillover                      0
ulStartCrb                          0
userLabel                           N305151E1
=====
Total: 1 Mos

```

Figure 63: Greek Testbed slicing definition.

5.3.2.2. gNodeB registration to the 5G Core SA

The testing was done with a VMVMVM running UERANSIM⁷ which is an open-source implementation of a 5G UE and RAN (gNodeB). It was used, to validate the slicing capabilities, protocol implementation of the 5G Core and conformance to the 3GPP Rel. 16 standards. The configuration of the gNodeB part of the UERANSIM, which has network interfaces to N1/N2 and N3, has two slices which are also defined in the 5G Core SA and have the values 5G SA: sst:1/sd: null , sst:2/sd:null.

The rararadio Interface - UERANSIM does not implement 5G radio protocols below the RRC alayera and 5G radio is partially simulated over the UDP protocol over port 4997... The registered UERANSIM gNodeB advertises the two slides configured, and this configuration is accepted by the 5G Core. Figure 64 below shows the NGAP setup request message.

Figure 64: NGAP setup request message.

The response message is shown in Figure 65 where the configuration is accepted by the 5G Core AMF.

⁷ <https://github.com/aligungr/UERANSIM>

Figure 65: NGAP setup response message.

5.3.2.2.1. UE configured with sst:2/sd:null

Figure 66: UE requesting a PDU session with NSSAI sst:2/sd:null.

Figure 66 shows the UE, with the PDU session configured with the aforementioned NSSAI, requesting a PDU session while Figure 67 shows the response which is successful i.e., the 5G Core accepts the slicing configuration.

Figure 67: PDU setup response.

Figure 68 and Figure 69 show the PDU session resource request showing also the requested NSSAI, maximum bit rate and 5QI info and the successful response.

Figure 68: PDU setup request with NSSAI, maximum bit rate and 5QI info.

No.	Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Length	Info
31	9.200357	172.25.3.5	172.25.3.174	NGAP/N...	262	PDU Session Resource Setup Request
32	9.200378	172.25.3.174	172.25.3.5	SCTP	62	SACK
33	9.209881	172.25.3.174	172.25.3.5	NGAP	106	PDU Session Resource Setup Response
34	9.317510	172.25.3.5	172.25.3.174	SCTP	62	SACK


```

Wireshark - Packet 33 - test7.pcap
  > Internet Protocol Version 4, Src: 172.25.3.174, Dst: 172.25.3.5
  > Stream Control Transmission Protocol, Src Port: 53846 (53846), Dst Port: 38412 (38412)
  > NG Application Protocol
    > NGAP-PDU: successfulOutcome (1)
      > successfulOutcome
        > procedureCode: id-PDU Session Resource Setup (29)
        > criticality: reject (0)
        > value
          > PDU Session Resource Setup Response
            > protocolIEs: 3 items
              > Item 0: id-AMF-UE-NGAP-ID
              > Item 1: id-RAN-UE-NGAP-ID
              > Item 2: id-PDU Session Resource Setup List SUsRes
                > ProtocolIE-Field
                  > id: id-PDU Session Resource Setup List SUsRes (75)
                  > criticality: ignore (1)
                  > value
                    > PDU Session Resource Setup List SUsRes: 1 item
                      > Item 0
                        > PDU Session Resource Setup Item SUsRes
                          > pduSessionID: 1
                          > PDU Session Resource Setup Response Transfer: 0003e0ac1903af000000010005
                            > dLQoSFlowPerTNLInformation
                              > uPTransportLayerInformation: gTPTunnel (0)
                                > gTPTunnel
                                  > transportLayerAddress: ac1903af [bit length 32, 1010 1100 0001 ...
                                  > gTP-TEID: 00000001
                                > associatedQoSFlowList: 1 item
                                  > Item 0
                                    > AssociatedQoSFlowItem
                                      > qosFlowIdentifier: 5
  
```

```

0000 fa 16 3e a8 3a 72 fa 16 3e b9 1d ac 08 00 45 02  ..>.:r.. >.....E:
0010 00 5c 00 00 40 00 40 84 db 36 ac 19 03 ae ac 19  -\..@.@. -6.....
  
```

Figure 69: PDU setup successful response.

5.3.2.2.2. UE configured with sst:1/sd:null

Another UE is configured in a similar fashion but in this case with NSSAI sst:1/sd:null.

Figure 70: PDU setup request.

Figure 70 shows the PDU setup request which includes the aforementioned NSSAI, maximum bit rate and 5QI identifier which is again 5 due to the fact that both slices were configured with the same 5QI. Figure 71 shows the successful response.

Figure 71: PDU response.

5.3.2.2.3. Configuration of 2 slices on the same UE

In addition, we configured two slices on the same UE, and noticed that it was possible to perform a setup request with two s-NSSAIs, as shown in Figure 72, while the successful response is shown in Figure 73.

Both PDU sessions are then established for each slice as shown in Figure 74 and Figure 75.

Figure 72: Initial context setup request involving two NSSAIs per UE.

Figure 73: Initial context setup response.

Figure 74: PDU session for NSSAI with sst:1.

Figure 75: Second PDU session for NSSAI with sst:2.

5.3.3. Management, Orchestration and Virtualized Infrastructure

The Management and Orchestration of operations in the Greek testbed are performed by the Open Source MANO OSM orchestrator (v. 12).

OSM is an operator-led ETSI community that is delivering a production-quality open-source Management and Orchestration (MANO) stack aligned with ETSI NFV Information Models and that targets to meet the requirements of production NFV networks.

OSM provides a full solution for NFV management and orchestration, covering both design time (i.e., DevOps) and run time phases of VNFs and Network Services lifecycle management.

The design-time scope of OSM includes: i) the capability for Create/Read/Update/Delete (CRUD) operations on the Network Service definition, ii) tools for VNF Package Generation, iii) Graphical User Interface (GUI) to accelerate the design time phase, VNFs on-boarding and deployment.

On the other hand, the run-time scope of OSM mostly provides: i) an automated Service Orchestration environment as the main coordination engine, ii) plugins for integrating multiple VIMs (including OpenStack, VMWare, Amazon Web Services, OpenVIM), iii) plugins for integrating multiple SDN controllers, iv) an integrated generic VNFM with support for integrating specific VNFMs from VNF vendors, v) support to integrate Physical Network Functions into Network Services.

The OSM dashboard’s main page for the created “VITAL-5G” project is shown below:

Figure 76: Greek testbed OSM deployment.

Openstack was selected as the Virtual Infrastructure Manager, sitting beneath OSM. OpenStack is a cloud operating system that controls large pools of compute, storage, and networking resources throughout a datacentre, all managed through i) its components’ APIs, ii) a command-line interface and iii) a dashboard, giving administrators control while empowering their users and in this case, the OSM orchestrator, to provision resources.

Figure 77: Greek testbed VIM integration.

To enable the instantiation of KNFs (Kubernetes-based Network Functions), a Kubernetes (K8s) master node is deployed, connected with the Virtual Networks of Openstack, and registered in OSM as a K8s cluster.

Figure 78: Greek testbed Openstack and K8s deployment.

Two instantiated Network Services that are used for the deployment of an IoT management Network App are show below to demonstrate the correct operation of the deployed system:

Name	Identifier	Nsd name	Operational Status	Config Status	Detailed Status	Actions
DEMO WP4 NXW - 1	b5e97239-d089-49e4-a1e3-c0b8a5771c67	iot-management-platform-ns	Running	Configured	Done	[Refresh] [Refresh] [Refresh] [Refresh] [Action]
demo instance NXW - wp4	34ccff5f-6fe9-405a-8143-79e20176dec	iot-management-platform-ns	Running	Configured	Done	[Refresh] [Refresh] [Refresh] [Refresh] [Action]

Figure 79: Greek testbed network services instantiation.

The Openstack instances that implement these Network Apps are shown below in the Openstack dashboard:

Instance Name	Image Name	IP Address	Flavor	Key Pair	Status	Availability Zone	Task	Power State	Age	Actions
demo instance NX-4-1-technicaldatavisualizationVM-0	vital-data-vis	192.168.1.209, 10.10.10.27	vital_flvr	vital	Active	us-east-1-nova	None	Running	2 hours, 54 minutes	Create Snapshot
demo instance NX-3-storageVM-0	vital-dash	192.168.1.109, 10.10.10.42	vital_flvr	vital	Active	us-east-1-nova	None	Running	2 hours, 55 minutes	Create Snapshot
demo instance NX-2-msgbrokerVM-0	vital-msg-broker	192.168.1.163, 10.10.10.43	vital_flvr	vital	Active	us-east-1-nova	None	Running	2 hours, 55 minutes	Create Snapshot
demo instance NX-1-HALVM-0	vital-hal10	192.168.1.53, 10.10.10.48	vital_flvr	vital	Active	us-east-1-nova	None	Running	2 hours, 55 minutes	Create Snapshot
DEMO WP4 NXW - 1-4-technicaldatavisualizationVM-0	vital-data-vis	192.168.1.108, 10.10.10.46	vital_flvr	vital	Active	us-east-1-nova	None	Running	3 hours, 47 minutes	Create Snapshot
DEMO WP4 NXW - 1-3-storageVM-0	vital-dash	192.168.1.68, 10.10.10.32	vital_flvr	vital	Active	us-east-1-nova	None	Running	3 hours, 47 minutes	Create Snapshot
DEMO WP4 NXW - 1-2-msgbrokerVM-0	vital-msg-broker	192.168.1.5, 10.10.10.31	vital_flvr	vital	Active	us-east-1-nova	None	Running	3 hours, 47 minutes	Create Snapshot
DEMO WP4 NXW - 1-1-HALVM-0	vital-hal10	192.168.1.65, 10.10.10.44	vital_flvr	vital	Active	us-east-1-nova	None	Running	3 hours, 48 minutes	Create Snapshot

Figure 80: Greek testbed Openstack Application deployment.

The network topology of the two deployments is shown below:

Figure 81: Greek testbed Openstack Network topology.

6. Platform and Testbed Integration

The VITAL-5G Platform is integrated with the 5G Testbeds through specific interfaces for the (1) Monitoring system, (2) 5G Slice Management System and (3) NFV MANO System, as described in D3.1 [5]. The detailed unified interfaces towards the VITAL-5G Platform are presented in D2.3 [3] for monitoring and slice management, while the interface with the NFV MANO system is based on the standard ETSI SOL interfaces already supported by OSM. For each testbed, the relevant plugins have been developed to handle the translation with the interfaces supported by the tools and platforms deployed in each testbed, as presented in detail in Table 15 and Figure 82.

Table 15: VITAL-5G Platform and Testbed Integration status.

VITAL-5G Interfaces/Testbed	Service & Network monitoring plugin	Multi-slice inventory and management plugin	Service orchestration plugin
Antwerp	100%	100% static slice	100%
Bucharest	100%	100% static slice 50% dynamics slice	100%
Greek	100%	100% static slice	100%

Figure 82: VITAL-5G Platform and testbed design and integration.

6.1. VITAL-5G platform slicing southbound interface

The southbound interface of the Slice inventory component is used to interact with the slice plugins deployed on each of the 5G testbeds, and it is leveraged for four main operations: 1) dynamic retrieval of 5G slice profile characteristics from each of the testbeds, ii) storing 5G slice-related information, iii) lifecycle management of 5G slices, and iv) slice allocation and querying.

Concerning the dynamic retrieval of 5G slice profile characteristics, when the slice is configured on the 5G testbed, either in a pre-configured or dynamic manner, the slice profile characteristics of this slice are reported to the Slice inventory. The overview of the endpoints used for this interaction is shown in Figure 83, Figure 84 and Figure 85. The goal of the dynamic retrieval of slice characteristics is to provide an up-to-date overview of available slices to any VITAL-5G Platform user that is interested in implementing the Network Apps and deploying them using the available 5G slices in a particular 5G testbed. More details about this feature of the Slice inventory are available in D2.3 [3].

Furthermore, once the slice-related information (i.e., configuration parameters, subscribers attached to it, testbed capabilities) is retrieved from the 5G testbeds, this information is stored in the Slice inventory database. In this integration phase, we have managed to test and integrate the capabilities of dynamically retrieving the slice-related information and storing this information for all three testbeds.

The slice-related information is further leveraged by the Slice inventory to perform slice allocation/querying and lifecycle management of network slices and based on the decisions to perform a particular LCM operation on the slice, this interface is used to communicate the decision with the slice plugins on the 5G testbeds. In particular, when an experiment is created and vertical services with Network Apps should be deployed, Slice inventory is in charge of selecting the suitable network slice if it is available, but if not, it sends the request to the slice plugin on the corresponding testbed to create the new slice or to dynamically reconfigure the existing one. This particular capability will be further extensively tested in the next phase of integration (Drop III).

POST a new URLLC slice

REQUEST BODY SCHEMA: application/json

sliceId required	string
site required	string
latency required	integer <int32>
jitter required	integer <int32>
expDataRateUL required	integer <int32>
expDataRateDL required	integer <int32>
trafficType required	string The type of traffic that is going over the URLLC slice.
imsi required	Array of strings The imsi's attached to that slice

Responses

— 200

Figure 83: Slice plugin reporting the creation of a new URLLC slice to the Slice inventory. A similar type of request applies to the eMBB type of slice.

Update a specific urllc slice in the Slice Inventory

REQUEST BODY SCHEMA: application/json

sliceId required	string
site required	string
latency required	integer <int32>
jitter required	integer <int32>
expDataRateUL required	integer <int32>
expDataRateDL required	integer <int32>
trafficType required	string The type of traffic that is going over the URLLC slice.
imsi required	Array of strings The imsi's attached to that slice

Responses

— 200

PUT /api/v1/sliceInventory/SB/reportSliceP...

Request samples

Payload

Content type
application/json

Copy Expand all Collapse all

```
{
  "sliceId": "AntwerpUllc01",
  "site": "antwerp",
  "latency": 14,
  "jitter": 1,
  "expDataRateUL": 100,
  "expDataRateDL": 100,
  "trafficType": "TCP",
  "imsi": [
    "imsi1",
    "imsi2",
    "imsi3"
  ]
}
```

Figure 84: Slice plugin updating an existing URLLC slice (dynamic slice management). A similar type of request applies to the eMBB type of slice.

Delete a specific urllc slice from the Slice Inventory

REQUEST BODY SCHEMA: application/json

sliceId required	string
site required	string
latency required	integer <int32>
jitter required	integer <int32>
expDataRateUL required	integer <int32>
expDataRateDL required	integer <int32>
trafficType required	string The type of traffic that is going over the URLLC slice.
imsi required	Array of strings The imsi's attached to that slice

Responses

— 200

DELETE /api/v1/sliceInventory/SB/reportSli...

Request samples

Payload

Content type
application/json

Copy Expand all Collapse all

```
{
  "sliceId": "AntwerpUllc01",
  "site": "antwerp",
  "latency": 14,
  "jitter": 1,
  "expDataRateUL": 100,
  "expDataRateDL": 100,
  "trafficType": "TCP",
  "imsi": [
    "imsi1",
    "imsi2",
    "imsi3"
  ]
}
```

Figure 85: Slice plugin deleting an existing URLLC slice. A similar type of request applies to the eMBB type of slice.

6.2. VITAL-5G platform monitoring southbound interface

The southbound interface of the VITAL-5G centralized monitoring platform is used for interfacing with the local monitoring systems deployed on each of the three 5G testbeds. This interfacing means the configuration of the ZeroMQ topics that are used for collecting different types of metrics/KPIs from the three trial sites. In particular, upon the creation of an experiment in the Vital-5G platform, the corresponding topic is created based on the

trigger from the Service LCM, and the centralized monitoring platform is dynamically configuring these topics on the relevant 5G testbed. The topic corresponds to the type of metric that local monitoring system needs to start publishing towards the centralized monitoring system.

The metrics measured in the three pilot sites and 5G testbeds can be retrieved either in real-time (with a certain frequency defined by local monitoring systems), or in a bulk format (depending on the type of experiment), and they belong to one of the following categories: infrastructure, network, services, and platform. Such collected metrics are further used by diagnostic elements that are in charge of detecting anomalies in service and network quality, as well as by the closed-loop mechanisms to act upon the detected events and perform the necessary reconfiguration of service and network functions. The southbound interface is entirely REST-based, and the available endpoints are presented in Figure 86.

Interface/request to local monitor ^

POST	/localtestbed/antwerp	Requested to start the collection of a metric.	▼
POST	/localtestbed/galati	Requested to start the collection of a metric.	▼
POST	/localtestbed/Athens	Requested to start the collection of a metric.	▼
POST	/localTestbed/stop/metric/publisher	Requested to stop the collection of a metric.	▼

Figure 86: Southbound interface of the monitoring platform.

6.3. Platform and Belgian Testbed Integration

At the Belgian 5G testbed side, we have successfully finalized the integration activities for the M23 milestone. In particular, the integration tests included: the onboarding, deploying, and instantiation of both the Network Apps and the vertical services, network/service/platform/infrastructure monitoring, and static slice management.

6.3.1. Network App onboarding and vertical instantiation

Concerning the onboarding and vertical service deployment activities, we successfully onboarded and deployed the entire vertical service 1, i.e., “Remote vessel monitoring”, which belongs to the UC1 within the Antwerp trial site, using the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI. The remote vessel monitoring vertical service consists of the following Network Apps: Onboard data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II (VS8), Monitoring dashboard (VS5), and Real-time digital twin (VA5). Real-time metrics coming from the Antwerp testbed can also be collected.

Below are the steps that we took in order to onboard, deploy, and instantiate the above-mentioned remote vessel monitoring vertical service, using the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI. All integration activities were performed using both OSM versions 10 and 12.

First, we successfully onboarded the three Network Apps, which compose our remote vessel monitoring vertical service, using the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI (Figure 87). This step involved uploading the correct zip file of the onboarded Network App and also the proper VNF Descriptors (VNFDs) that correspond to Network Apps in the vertical service, as well as the Network Service Descriptors (NSDs) of the entire vertical service.

Figure 87: Onboarding blueprints of Network Apps in the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI; Network Apps used in this example are building the Remote vessel monitoring vertical service.

After a successful blueprint onboarding, the Network App blueprints are displayed in the Antwerp local OSM, as shown in Figure 88.

Figure 88: The onboarded Net Apps are available on the Antwerp local OSM.

The next step is to onboard and instantiate the remote vessel monitoring vertical service on the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI. This step has been performed by uploading the NSD of vertical service 1 through the Portal Web GUI, and the outcome is showcased in Figure 89.

Figure 89: Successfully instantiated the remote vessel monitoring vertical service through the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI.

The result of the successful deployment of the vertical service instance (i.e., remote vessel monitoring vertical service) using the local OSM deployment is shown in Figure 90. Finally, the deployed instance of the remote vessel monitoring vertical service is spawned up on top of the local OpenStack, where all Network Apps are running as VM instances in the OpenStack environment (Figure 91). Thus, all Network Apps that compose the vertical service for remote vessel monitoring are up and running in the OpenStack environment as VMs. They are attached to the proper pre-configured OpenStack network in order to be able to communicate with each other.

Figure 90: The remote vessel monitoring vertical service successfully instantiated on the local OSM.

Figure 91: The remote vessel monitoring vertical service was successfully instantiated on the local OSM.

6.3.2. Monitoring

Once the remote vessel monitoring vertical service is up and running, monitoring of its performance, as well as the performance of the underlying network and NFV infrastructure, is started. Since the Belgian testbed is also integrated with VITAL-5G centralized monitoring platform, real-time metrics can be retrieved from the 5G testbed. The local monitoring system located at the Belgian testbed is in charge of publishing the requested metrics towards the VITAL-5G centralized monitoring platform.

We have tested a real-time collection of various metrics (network, infrastructure, service, platform). As examples, in Figure 92, Figure 93, and Figure 94, we show the real-time influx of the network metric “latency”, infrastructure metric “cpu_usage” of the Network App VS8, and service metric “quality of experience” (elaborated at the application level). This overview shows the proper work of monitoring capability on the 5G testbed and its integration with the centralized monitoring system that is running on the VITAL-5G platform. It is worth mentioning that prior to performing a real-time collection of metrics, the corresponding topics are configured on the local monitoring system on the 5G testbed, based on the requests received from the centralized monitoring system.

Figure 92: A real-time influx of network latency in the Belgian 5G testbed.

Figure 93 A real-time influx of CPU load in the Belgian 5G testbed

Figure 94: A real-time influx of quality experience in the Belgian 5G testbed.

6.3.3. Static network slicing

As one of the integration activities, static network slicing and interfacing between the slice plugin on the Belgian 5G testbed and the slice inventory on the VITAL-5G platform have been developed and tested. The capabilities that have been tested in this release and integration phase are limited to real-time reporting of slice profiles available in the 5G network on the Belgian testbed (Figure 95). These activities include the very first report on the preconfigured network slices (both URLLC and eMBB) so that the slice inventory component can store those profiles in the database, and use the available information when deciding where to deploy a particular vertical service, and to which slice to attach the corresponding user.

Besides the activities of reporting the profiles of the preconfigured network slices, in this phase we have also managed to test updating an existing slice based on the manual change of slice parameters (Figure 96, Figure 97 and Figure 98), and the deletion of preconfigured network slices. In the next integration phase, the complete performance of slicing capabilities and slice plugin will be tested, including the interaction between Service LCM and Slice inventory, which results in certain dynamic changes in the slice profiles on the 5G testbed.

```

2022-12-16 09:59:24.130 INFO 25554 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] b.i.i.v.s.service.UrllcSliceService : Successfully stored the new slice with ID: AntwerpUrllc01 of the site: antwerp
2022-12-16 10:00:43.136 INFO 25554 --- [0.0-8080-exec-3] b.i.i.v.s.service.EmbbSliceService : Successfully stored the new slice with ID: AntwerpEmbb01 of the site: antwerp
2022-12-16 10:02:36.358 INFO 25554 --- [0.0-8080-exec-5] b.i.i.v.s.service.UrllcSliceService : Successfully updated the Urllc slice for: AntwerpUrllc01
2022-12-16 10:03:48.058 INFO 25554 --- [0.0-8080-exec-7] b.i.i.v.s.service.EmbbSliceService : Successfully updated the slice with ID: AntwerpEmbb01
2022-12-16 10:04:25.692 INFO 25554 --- [0.0-8080-exec-8] b.i.i.v.s.service.EmbbSliceService : Successfully delete the slice: AntwerpEmbb01
    
```

Figure 95: The report on the successful action of storing slice-related information in the Slice inventory database.

```

sliceinventory=# select * from embb_slice;
 id | area_traffic_capdl | area_traffic_capul | exp_data_ratedl | exp_data_rateul | site | slice_id | traffic_type | user_density | user_speed
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----
  1 |          200 |          200 |          200 |          200 | Antwerp | AntwerpEmbb01 | UDP |          200 |          80
(1 row)

sliceinventory=# select * from embb_slice_imsi;
 embb_slice_id | imsi
-----+-----
              1 | imsi1
              1 | imsi2
              1 | imsi3
              1 | imsi4
(4 rows)
    
```

Figure 96: The details of the eMBB slice within the Antwerp testbed (slice parameters).

```

sliceinventory=# select * from urllc_slice;
 id | exp_data_rateul | exp_data_rateul | jitter | latency | site | slice_id | traffic_type
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----
  1 |          100 |          100 |     1 |        16 | Antwerp | AntwerpUrllc01 | UDP
(1 row)

sliceinventory=# select * from urllc_slice_imsi;
 urllc_slice_id | imsi
-----+-----
           1 | imsi1
           1 | imsi2
           1 | imsi3
           1 | imsi4
(4 rows)
    
```

Figure 97: The details of the URLLC slice within the Antwerp testbed (slice parameters).

```

sliceinventory=# select * from urllc_slice;
 id | exp_data_rateul | exp_data_rateul | jitter | latency | site | slice_id | traffic_type
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----
  1 |          100 |          100 |     1 |        14 | antwerp | AntwerpUrllc01 | TCP
(1 row)

sliceinventory=# select * from urllc_slice_imsi;
 urllc_slice_id | imsi
-----+-----
           1 | imsi1
           1 | imsi2
           1 | imsi3
(3 rows)
    
```

Figure 98: The details of the updated URLLC slice within the Antwerp testbed (slice parameters).

6.4. Platform and Romanian Testbed Integration

The Romanian testbed is fully integrated with the VITAL-5G Platform for LCM SOL006 Interface, Monitoring and Slice interfaces, using the plugins developed by ORO for VITAL-5G Platform interactions, as described below.

6.4.1. Service orchestration plugin

The service orchestration plugin is embedded in the SOL006 NBI of the Romanian testbed orchestrator, directly connected to the VITAL-5G Platform. The testing of deployment and other lifecycle management actions triggered by the VITAL-5G Platform is successful on OSM, as described in the following examples.

Figure 99: Romanian testbed Network Apps successful instantiation status message.

NS Instances

● init
 ● running / configured
 ● failed
 ● scaling

Name	Identifier	Nsd name	Operational Status	Config Status	Detailed Status
Video traffic VS9 - take 5	155ac1d3-3616-42d4-a330-bd272e512784	vs9-ns	✔	✔	Done
Video traffic take 4	ba22884b-3d96-459f-a31c-1081d8096856	vs9-ns	⚠	⚠	scheduled
oro_vnf	3505ce76-5510-4824-afcd-7edf6cfcdc91	traffic-generation-ns	✔	✔	Done

Figure 100: Romanian testbed visualisation at OSM level.

Instances

Instance Name	Image Name	IP Address	Flavor	Key Pair	Status	Availability Zone	Task	Power State	Age	Ac
Video traffic V-1-ubuntu-VM-0	ubuntu-18-04-server-video-netapp	192.168.32.190	beia.xlarge	-	Active	nova	None	Running	8 minutes	C
oro_vnf-1-ubuntu-VM-0	Ubuntu-18.04	192.168.32.192	cirros-VM-flv	-	Active	nova	None	Running	3 hours, 56 minutes	C

Figure 101: Romanian testbed visualisation at Openstack level.

6.4.2. Monitoring plugin

The Monitoring Plugin in the Romanian testbed is an application built in python using Flask Web framework and following the high-level architecture represented in Figure 102.

Figure 102: Romanian testbed monitoring plugin.

It is used to translate the specific metrics requested from the VITAL-5G Centralised Monitoring Platform and to expose them on a dedicated queue and port that is correlated to the type of resource that is necessary to be monitored and delivered. The plugin is available on the Git⁸, through the network metrics publisher.

The plugin exposes two main API calls, as defined:

- localTestbed/galati
 - Used to start a collection of requested metrics using a specific process and topic, there will be produced values for metrics (start metric collection)
- localTestbed/stop/metric/publisher
- Used to stop the process for specific topics and metrics when requested by the Centralised Platform (stop metrics collection)

The Romanian testbed is able to collect and publish various metrics, as described in D4.1 95_(CPU Load, RAM, Latency, Network), some examples as seen in Figure 103, Figure 104 and Figure 104.

⁸ <https://gitlab.com/vital-5g>

Figure 103: Romanian testbed monitoring infrastructure CPU monitoring.

Figure 104: Romanian testbed monitoring End-to-End slice Latency monitoring.

6.4.3. Slice Inventory and management Plugin

Slice Plugin RO 5G SA is a python application that is using the Flask Web framework and it is working as a proxy for the Slice Inventory component of the VITAL-5G project infrastructure.

This plugin ensures that the centralised VITAL-5G Slicing management component is able to obtain or modify information about users and slices as described in D2.3 [3].

At this milestone, the Slice Plugin is developed using three main components, as described below, adapting the Romanian testbed capabilities to VITAL-5G platform APIs:

- retrieve data about a specific slice and slice users (using a GET API call), translating the VITAL-5G platform call request into specific testbed API call

Example of Testbed API call for slice inventory, following testbed APIs existing Southbound Interfaces, results presented at the VITAL-5G Platform level:

GET https://APC-IP:<port>/apc/v2/udr/1/udr/ngc-profiles

Results are described by the next figure, highlighting the variety of slice profiles in the testbed.

```

sliceinventory=# select * from urllc_slice;
 id | exp_data_rateul | exp_data_rateul | jitter | latency | site | slice_id | traffic_type
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----
  1 | 1000 | 1000 | 1 | 10 | galati | Galati_merged_EMBB_URLLC | critical
  2 | 1000 | 1000 | 1 | 10 | galati | Galati_URLLC | critical
(2 rows)

sliceinventory=# select * from urllc_slice_imsi;
 urllc_slice_id | imsi
-----+-----
 1 | 226107900000077
 2 | 226107900000001
 2 | 226107900000009
 2 | 226107900000075
(4 rows)
    
```

Figure 105: Romanian testbed slice inventory output.

Example of Testbed API call for slice profile, in this example an uRLLC slice descriptor, as seen in Figure 106.

GET https://APC-IP:<port>/apc/v2/udr/1/udr/ngc-profiles/eMBB2

```

sliceinventory=# select * from urllc_slice;
 id | exp_data_rateul | exp_data_rateul | jitter | latency | site | slice_id | traffic_type
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----
  1 | 1000 | 1000 | 1 | 10 | galati | Galati_merged_EMBB_URLLC | critical
(1 row)
    
```

Figure 106: Romanian testbed eMBB2 slice configuration.

Example of Testbed API call for subscriber slice profile, as seen in Figure 106 GET https://APC-IP:<port>/apc/v2/udr/1//uiccs/<subscriber-ID>.

```

sliceinventory=# select * from urllc_slice_imsi;
 urllc_slice_id | imsi
-----+-----
 1 | 226107900000077
(1 row)
    
```

Figure 107: Romanian testbed subscriber attached to slice (eMBB).

- Attach or override a specific subscriber to a slice, (using a POST API call), translating the VITAL-5G platform call request into specific testbed API call
- PUT https://https://APC-IP:<port>/apc/v2/udr/1/udr/subscribers/<subscriber name>' -T add_sub_with_PUT.json -H "Content-Type: application/json" Remove a specific subscriber
- DELETE 'https://APC-IP:<port>apc/v2/udr/1/udr/subscribers/<Subscriber name>'

The dynamics E2E slice creation is in ongoing activities for testing and validation. All the experiments can be run now in a manual slice configuration mode.

6.5. Platform and Greek Testbed Integration

6.5.1. Monitoring Integration

The Greek Testbed Monitoring Plugin is an application built in Python using the Flask web framework and implements the architecture shown in Figure 108.

Figure 108: Monitoring plugin architecture of the Greek testbed.

The Centralised Monitoring Platform uses an interface with the Local Monitoring Agent to request the exposure of individual experiment metrics. The Local Monitoring Agent, based on those requests, retrieves these metrics and exposes them to the Centralised Monitoring Platform using ZeroMQ publishers on the predefined ports, 2050-2053 for the various metric categories. The local agent exposes two functionalities to start and stop the publishing of the requested metric.

The collection of the supported metrics is handled in two ways. The network metrics are collected from the network infrastructure and exposed on the Network Monitoring system using Prometheus. For the collection of the service and infrastructure metrics two different implementations are supported. The first one utilises custom probes that are embedded into the service components capable of collecting typical infrastructure metrics, as well as custom service metrics. These probes can be preconfigured, configured with day-1/2 configuration actions after instantiation or configured remotely after the experiment has started. The probes receive the instance specific information, such as service identifier, VM identifier, etc., via their environment in order to provide the appropriate labels to the exposed metrics for filtering by the local monitoring agent. The second uses an intermediate exporter that receives the generated metrics directly using ZeroMQ sockets, in the same way the Centralised platform does, and then exports those metrics to the service monitoring Prometheus instance.

6.5.2. Slicing Integration

The slicing plugin of the Greek testbed, is an application build in Java and uses the Spring Boot Framework⁹. It translates the southbound interface of the platform which is presented in section 6.1 to appropriate actions on the 5G SA Core which are presented in the section below.

6.5.2.1. Southbound interface towards the 5G Core SA

Authentication to the 5G Core

To get the authentication token from the 5G Core, the plugin implements the following API, which can be showcased with the following curl command:

```
curl--location-request POST 'https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/auth/login' \
--header 'Content-Type: application/json' \
--data-raw '{
"username": "USERNAME_HERE",
```

⁹ <https://spring.io/>

```
"password": "PASSWORD_HERE"
}'
```

In the response to the POST request, the plugin, looks for the ACCESS_TOKEN, as shown in the following example.

```
curl --location --request GET 'ENDPOINT' --header 'Authorization: Bearer ACCESS_TOKEN_HERE'
```

After getting an authentication token, the next requests to the system can be performed.

Retrieve Provisioned Data profiles list

The plugin uses the following API to retrieve the complete list of Provisioned Data Profiles:

```
curl -k -X GET "https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/provisioned_data_profiles"
```

Retrieve Single Provisioned Data profiles info

The following API retrieves information on a specific provisioned Profile:

```
curl -k -X GET "https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/provisioned_data_profiles/{uuid}"
```

In the current example {uuid} is changed with the required UUID address.

Delete Single Provisioned Data profiles

The following API allows to delete an existing Provisioned Data Profile

```
curl -k -X DELETE
"https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/provisioned_data_profiles/{uuid}"
```

In the current example {uuid} is a placeholder and changed with the required UUID address.

Create a new Provisioned Data Profile

The following API creates a new Provisioned Data Profile.

```
curl -k -X POST "https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/provisioned_data_profiles" -H
"Content-Type: application/json" -d @./provisioned_data_profile_create.json
```

The reader should refer to Annex II: 5G Core Data Profiles for the Greek Testbed for the actual structure of the provisioned data profile (file provisioned_data_profile_create.json)

Replace (or create) a new Provisioned Data Profile

This API replaces an existing Provisioned Data profile (or creates a new one if it doesn't exist).

```
curl -k -X PUT "https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/provisioned_data_profiles" -H
"Content-Type: application/json" -d @./provisioned_data_profile_replace.json
```

The reader should refer to Annex II: 5G Core Data Profiles for the Greek Testbed for the actual structure of the provisioned data profile (file provisioned_data_profile_create.json)

Retrieve a PLMN rule for an existing Provisioned Data Profile

This API retrieves the rule for a specific PLMN of an existing provisioned data profile

```
curl -k -X GET
"https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/provisioned_data_profiles/{uuid}/{plmn}"
```

In the current example {uuid} and {plmn} are changed to the required uuid and plmn values.

Create or replace a PLMN rule for an existing Provisioned Data Profile

This API creates a new rule (or replaces an existing one) for a specific PLMN for an existing Provisioned Data Profile.

```
curl -k -X PUT
"https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/provisioned_data_profiles/{uuid}/{plmn}" -H
"Content-Type: application/json" -d @./replace_rule.json
```

The reader should refer to Annex II: 5G Core Data Profiles for the Greek Testbed for the actual structure of the replace data profile(file replace_rule.json)

Delete a PLMN Rule for a Provisioned Data Profile

This API deletes an existing PLMN rule for a Provisioned Data Profile.

```
curl -k -X DELETE
  "https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/provisioned_data_profiles/{uuid}/{plmn}"
```

In the current example {uuid} and {plmn} are changed to the required uuid and plmn values. **Replace Data Profile Policy associated to an existing SUPI**

This API replaces the policy data profile associated to an existing SUPI:

```
curl -k -X PUT "https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/supis/{supi}/policy_data_profile"
  -H "Content-Type: application/json" -d @./supi_replace_policy.json
```

In the current example {SUPI} is a placeholder. Change it with the desired SUPI.

The json file “supi_replace_policy.json” should have a structure like the following one:

```
{
  "uuid": "ea12e83e-3990-4c93-b873-beba9dceafb3"
}
```

“uuid”: “ea12e83e-3990-4c93-b873-beba9dceafb3” is a sample value.

Replace provisioned Data Profile associated to an existing SUPI

This API replaces the provisioned data profile associated to an existing SUPI:

```
curl -k -X PUT
  "https://5gcore_api_endpoint/api/1/provisioning/supis/{supi}/provisioned_data_profile" -H
  "Content-Type: application/json" -d @./supi_replace_profile.json
```

In the current example {SUPI} is a placeholder. It should be changed with the desired supi.

The json file “supi_replace_profile.json” should have a structure like the following one:

```
{
  "uuid": "ea12e83e-3990-4c93-b873-beba9dceafb3"
}
```

“uuid”: “ea12e83e-3990-4c93-b873-beba9dceafb3” is a sample value.

7. Conclusion

The VITAL-5G platform has been integrated both in its entirety and with the three testbeds. All components of the platform are running in the production environment and its southbound interfaces for the monitoring, slicing and orchestration are integrated with the corresponding interfaces of the three testbeds.

The three testbeds are themselves integrated both in the 5G Core and their virtualized infrastructure level with the orchestration, monitoring and slicing management functions of the platform. Static slicing is available for the Drop II release of the platform of all testbeds, while dynamic slicing will be available for the final release in Drop III.

The deliverable outputs is demonstrating in details that the requested network upgrades and software implementation have been performed, the VITAL-5G system components are integrated, as planned from the functionality perspective and the platform functional tests is proving the operational readiness of the system, running in the live 5G environment, by delivering the end-to-end system for T&L Infrastructure and also being capable to support the 3rd parties experimenters in the open 5G environment.

The deliverable is demonstrating at Drop II the intermediate VITAL-5G integrated system and operational readiness results, correlated to the components development and following several steps for validation of the functionality. We conclude that at this milestone we have delivered the first full version of the E2E VITAL-5G system (including Network Applications, open repository and tools), now available for full trials experiments from internal and 3rd party partners.

Even if the VITAL-5G Platform and the 5G testbeds are now implemented from the network and 5G SA services perspective, ready for 3rd party experimentation in the production environment, we will continue to validate and extend the system, integrating the new features that will become available from the development activities in WP2 to improve the 5G services provided, and identifying, reporting and fixing, during next period, all the bugs and malfunctional behaviours.

The final integration and implementation, including Drop IIIIII activities, will be reported through the VITAL-5G final integrated and operational system, that will be delivered by M30, delivering the full final version of the E2E VITAL-5G system ready, including enhancements developed on the basis of feedback romromfrom3rd party experimenters.

8. References

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- [3] VITAL-5G, Deliverable D2.3, “VITAL-5G experimentation platform & Open Repository – first full version”, November 2022
- [4] VITAL-5G, Deliverable D2.2, “VITAL-5G experimentation platform – Early (testing) drop”, March 2022, https://www.vital5g.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/VITAL5G-D2.2_VITAL-5G_experimentation_platform_Early_testing_drop_v1.0.pdf
- [5] VITAL-5G, Deliverable D3.1, “Report on VITAL-5G infrastructure upgrades & extensions”, March 2022, https://www.vital5g.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/VITAL-5G_D3.1-Report-on-VITAL-5G-infrastructure-upgrades-extensions_v1.0.pdf
- [6] VITAL-5G, Deliverable D1.1, “Report on use case requirements – Version 2.0”, April 2022, https://www.vital5g.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/VITAL5G-D1.1_Report-on-Use-case-requirements-v2.0.pdf
- [7] VITAL-5G, Deliverable D4.1, “Trial planning and experimentation methodology”, June 2022

Annex I: Integration Plan

Workflow Level Status Dashboards

In this section, the sprint analysis of the Network App Package Onboarding, Vertical Service Instantiation and Experiment Creation Execution and Monitoring Status Dashboards will be presented.

WBS	Task description	SW Components	Responsible	Integration Status	Start date	Finish date	Progress
1	Drop 1 (M15)				4/1/2022	4/5/2022	100%
1.1	Netapp Package Onboarding				4/1/2022	4/5/2022	100%
1.1.1	Sprint 1.1 Onboard, retrieval and deletion NetApp Package drop 1	Portal Web GUI, NetApps Services & Experiments Catalogue	eBOS, NXW	5.Integrated	4/1/2022	4/5/2022	100%
1.1.2	Sprint 1.2 Standalone NetApp Validation	NetApp Validator	BEIA	5.Integrated	4/1/2022	4/5/2022	100%

Diagram annotations: Platform Drop (points to WBS 1), Group of Sprints (points to WBS 1.1), Integration Sprints (points to WBS 1.1.1 and 1.1.2), Drop progress (points to Progress 100%), Group Progress (points to Progress 100%), Sprint Progress (points to Progress 100%).

Network App Package Onboarding

The descriptions of each Sprint are shown in Table 16. For more details, please refer to the implementation deliverables D2.1 [2] and D2.3 [3].

Table 16: Description of the Network App Package Onboarding Sprints.

Sprint	Description
Sprint 1.1 Onboard, retrieval and deletion Network App Package Drop I	Onboard, retrieval and deletion of a Network App into the Network Apps Services & Experiments Catalogue through the Portal Web GUI
Sprint 1.2 Standalone Network App Validation	Standalone Network App validation by using the Network App Validator API
Sprint 1.3 Onboarding Vertical Service Blueprint	Onboarding of a Vertical Services Blueprint through the Portal Web GUI to the Network Apps Services & Experiments Catalogue
Sprint 1.4 Retrieval Vertical Service Blueprint	Retrieval of a Vertical Services Blueprint from the Network Apps Services & Experiments Catalogue through the Portal Web GUI
Sprint 1.5 Deletion Vertical Service Blueprint	Deletion of a Vertical Services Blueprint from the Network Apps Services & Experiments Catalogue through the Portal Web GUI
Sprint 1.6 NSD onboarding	Onboarding a Network Service Descriptor to the Network Apps Services & Experiments Catalogue through the Portal Web GUI
Sprint 1.7 Onboard VNF Package to GUI	Onboard of a VNF Package to the Portal Web GUI through its web interface.
Sprint 1.8 Get URL and credentials to reach NFVO	Network App Services & Experiments Catalogue gets the URL and credentials from the Multi-Site Inventory to reach the OSM of a specific testbed
Sprint 1.9 Onboard VNF & NSD Package to NFVO, Bucharest	Onboard a VNF & NSD from the Network Apps Services & Experiments Catalogue the Bucharest testbed OSM

Sprint 1.10 Onboard VNF & NSD Package to NFVO, Antwerp	Onboard a VNF & NSD from the Network Apps Services & Experiments Catalogue the Antwerp testbed OSM
Sprint 1.11 Onboard VNF & NSD Package to NFVO, Greek	Onboard a VNF & NSD from the Network Apps Services & Experiments Catalogue the Greek testbed OSM
Sprint 1.12 Onboard Network App Package, Bucharest testbed	Onboard Network App package through the Portal Web GUI to the Network App Services & Experiments Catalogue, verify Network App compatibility with the Bucharest testbed through the Multi-Site Inventory, validate the Network App through the Network App Validator and upload it to the Bucharest testbed OSM
Sprint 1.13 Onboard Network App Package, Antwerp testbed	Onboard Network App package through the Portal Web GUI to the Network App Services & Experiments Catalogue, verify Network App compatibility with the Antwerp testbed through the Multi-Site Inventory, validate the Network App through the Network App Validator and upload it to the Antwerp testbed OSM
Sprint 1.14 Onboard Network App Package, Greek testbed	Onboard Network App package through the Portal Web GUI to the Network App Services & Experiments Catalogue, verify Network App compatibility with the Greek testbed through the Multi-Site Inventory, validate the Network App through the Network App Validator and upload it to the Greek testbed OSM
Sprint 1.15 Validate Network App Package though backend	Validate a Network App from the Network App Services & Experiments Catalogue through the Network App Validator
Sprint 1.16 Validate Network App Package through GUI	Validate a Network App from GUI through the Network App Validator

Vertical Services Instantiation

Table 17: Description of the Vertical Services Instantiation Sprints.

Sprint	Description
Sprint 2.1 Onboard, verify and return VSD ID from backend	Onboard, verify and return VSD ID from Network Apps Services & Experiments Catalogue through its API
Sprint 2.2 Instantiate Vertical Service & return VS ID from backend	Instantiate Vertical Service & return VS ID from Network Apps Services & Experiments Catalogue through its API
Sprint 2.3 Get VSD, VSB, NABs and translate into NSD and slice profile	Service LCM gets VSD, VSB & NABs from Network Apps Services & Experiments Catalogue and translate into target NSD and slice profile
Sprint 2.4 Specify VSD	The user onboards the VSD through the Portal Web GUI.
Sprint 2.5 Onboard, verify and return VSD ID	The user onboards the VSD (Service parameters, target testbed) through the Portal Web GUI to the Network Apps Services & Experiments Catalogue which verifies the VSD and returns a VSD ID
Sprint 2.6 Instantiation of a Vertical	The user instantiates a VS (Vertical Service) through the Portal

Service	Web GUI which in turn instantiates it to the Service LCM. The latter generates a VS ID and returns it to the GUI
Sprint 2.7 Get testbed info (NFVO, 5G slicing capabilities)	The Service LCM translates the VSD, VSB and NABs into target NSD, 5G Slice Profile and gets the testbed information through the Multi-Site Inventory
Sprint 2.8 Config network slice and return Network Slice ID	The Service LCM configures the network slice for specific UEs through the Multi-Site 5G Slice Inventory
Sprint 2.9 Create network slice Bucharest testbed	The Multi-site 5G slice inventory configures the 5G Slice Management Bucharest Plugin
Sprint 2.10 Select network slice profile and configure network slice, Antwerp testbed	The Multi-site 5G slice inventory configures the 5G Slice Management Antwerp Plugin
Sprint 2.11 Select network slice profile and configure network slice, Greek testbed	The Multi-site 5G slice inventory configures the 5G Slice Management Greek Plugin
Sprint 2.12 Deploy & Exchange Network Service with Network Apps (NSD and params), Bucharest Testbed	The Service LCM deploys and instantiates a Network Service with Network Apps (NSD and parameters) through the OSM of the Bucharest testbed to the VIM. The OSM returns NS ID.
Sprint 2.13 Deploy & Exchange Network Service with Network Apps (NSD and params), Antwerp Testbed	The Service LCM deploys and instantiates a Network Service with Network Apps (NSD and parameters) through the OSM of the Antwerp testbed to the VIM. The OSM returns NS ID.
Sprint 2.14 Deploy & Exchange Network Service with Network Apps (NSD and params), Greek Testbed	The Service LCM deploys and instantiates a Network Service with Network Apps (NSD and parameters) through the OSM of the Greek testbed to the VIM. The OSM returns NS ID.
Sprint 2.15 Configuration of Vertical Service and Network App Metrics & KPIs	The Service LCM configures the Vertical Service and KPI metrics through the Monitoring Platform.
Sprint 2.16 Configure Services and Network KPI Metrics, Bucharest Testbed	The Service LCM configures the network KPI metrics through the Monitoring Bucharest Testbed Plugin
Sprint 2.17 Configure Services and Network KPI Metrics, Antwerp Testbed	The Service LCM configures the network KPI metrics through the Monitoring Antwerp Testbed Plugin
Sprint 2.18 Configure Services and Network KPI Metrics, Greek Testbed	The Service LCM configures the network KPI metrics through the Monitoring Greek Testbed Plugin
Sprint 2.19 Publish Monitoring Data, Bucharest Testbed	The Monitoring Bucharest Testbed Plugin publishes monitoring data to the Service and Network Monitoring
Sprint 2.20 Publish Monitoring Data, Antwerp Testbed	The Monitoring Antwerp Testbed Plugin publishes monitoring data to the Service and Network Monitoring
Sprint 2.21 Publish Monitoring Data, Greek Testbed	The Monitoring Greek Testbed Plugin publishes monitoring data to the Service and Network Monitoring
Sprint 2.22 Retrieval of Vertical Services	The user, through the Portal Web GUI retrieves Vertical Services

Information	information (Network Apps info, 5G Slices info, KPIs info...) by sending the VS ID from the Service LCM
Sprint 2.23 Validate licence	The Service LCM validates the licences of watch Network App through the Licence Manager

Experiment Creation, Execution and Monitoring

The description of each Sprint is shown in Table 18.

Table 18: Description of the Experiment Creation, Execution and Monitoring Sprints.

Sprints	Description
Sprint 3.1 Initial Support for Experiment LCM	Create an experiment to the Experiment LCM through its API
Sprint 3.2 Specify ExpD	The user uploads an Experiment Descriptor through the Portal Web GUI
Sprint 3.3 Onboard, verify and return ExpD ID	The Portal Web GUI onboards the ExpD to the Network App Services & Experiments Catalogue and gets a ExpD ID
Sprint 3.4 Create experiment and get ExpB, ExpD	The user proceeds with the request for the creation of the experiment, specifying its ExpD ID, the ID of the Vertical Service (previously instantiated) which is associated with the experiment and a number of configuration parameters for tuning the conditions of the testing environment and the test execution. The request is forwarded from the Portal Web GUI to the Experiment LCM. It retrieves ExpB and ExpD from the Network App Services & Experiments Catalogue
Sprint 3.5 Lock VS_ID, generate Exp_ID and export it to GUI	The Experiment LCM locks the vertical service on the Service LCM. It should be noted that only a single experiment is permitted over a vertical service instance, in order to avoid overlapping test executions; as a consequence, if the vertical service is already locked the experiment is rejected. If the experiment can be accepted, the Service Testing & Experiment Manager creates a new entry in its record and returns the unique experiment ID (Exp_ID in the picture).
Sprint 3.6 Launch experiment execution	Launch of the experiment execution though the Portal Web GUI, to the Experiment LCM.
Sprint 3.7 Configure Monitoring (KPIs)	Configuration of KPIs from the Experiment LCM to the Service & Network Monitoring
Sprint 3.8 Configure Network Apps (Testing config), Bucharest Testbed	The Experiment LCM configures Network Apps though the Bucharest testbed OSM

Sprint 3.9 Configure Network Apps (Testing config), Antwerp Testbed	The Experiment LCM configures Network Apps through the Antwerp testbed OSM
Sprint 3.10 Configure Network App (Testing config), Greek Testbed	The Experiment LCM configures Network Apps through the Greek testbed OSM
Sprint 3.11 Configure Result Analytics Validation (Results, KPIs, Validation Criteria)	The Experiment LCM configures the Results Analytics/AI Based Diagnostics notifying the launch of the experiment execution and triggering the computation of the KPIs.
Sprint 3.12 Execute test scripts on Network Apps, Bucharest Testbed	The Experiment LCM executes test scripts through the Bucharest testbed OSM.
Sprint 3.13 Execute Test Scripts on Network Apps, Antwerp Testbed	The Experiment LCM executes test scripts through the Antwerp testbed OSM.
Sprint 3.14 Execute Test Scripts on Network Apps, Greek Testbed	The Experiment LCM executes test scripts through the Greek testbed OSM.
Sprint 3.15 Collect Experiment Metrics, compute and publish KPIs	The Result Analytics/AI Diagnostics publish the computed KPIs to the Service & Network Monitoring
Sprint 3.16 Stop experiment execution	User stops the experiment and Experiment LCM notifies the Result Analytics to stop execution. If the diagnostic feature is enabled, the Results Analytic further interacts with the AI-based Diagnostic component to trigger the performance diagnosis algorithms.
Sprint 3.17 Request experiment validation and create results report	An experiment result report is generated and made available for the user
Sprint 3.18 Clean Network Apps testing configuration, Bucharest Testbed	The Service LCM cleans up all the testing configuration previously applied to the Network Apps through the Bucharest testbed OSM and updates the internal experiment record.
Sprint 3.19 Clean Network App testing configuration, Antwerp Testbed	The Service LCM cleans up all the testing configuration previously applied to the Network Apps through the Antwerp testbed OSM and updates the internal experiment record.
Sprint 3.20 Clean Network App testing configuration, Greek Testbed	The Service LCM cleans up all the testing configuration previously applied to the Network Apps through the Greek testbed OSM and updates the internal experiment record

Integration Reporting Template

Below you can find a sample of the reporting template for the conclusion of the integration of each of the integration Sprints or a group of them.

Table 19: Integration reporting template.

Integration Sprint(s)	Platform Components	Date
2.1.1 Sprint 2.4 Specify VSD 2.1.2 Sprint 2.5 Onboard, verify and return VSD ID 2.1.3 Sprint 2.6 Instantiation of a Vertical Service 2.1.4 Sprint 2.7 Get testbed info (NFVO, 5G slicing capabilities)	Portal Web GUI, NetApp Validator, NetApp Catalogue, Antwerp OSM, Antwerp Openstack	17/11/2022
Partners	IMEC, NXW, EBOS,	
Validation Method	Create VSD and Instantiate Vertical service through the Portal Web GUI	
Prerequisites		
Validation Conditions (KPIs)	{Describe the KPIs}	
Results		
Request Body	Parameters Request	Parameters Response
{Json}		
Comments	Vertical service instantiation concluded successfully Monitoring configuration performed successfully Grafana panels created Blocking issue: Grafana requires authentication when embedded on the GUI	
Gitlab Issues	https://gitlab.com/vital-5g-private/vital-5g_platform/monitoring-platform/-/issues/1	
Result	Partial Pass	

Annex II: 5G Core Data Profiles for the Greek Testbed

Provisioned Data Profile

The provisioned data profile should have a structure like the following one:

```
{
  "description":"profile-1",
  "plmn_rules_map":{
    "*":{
      "action":"DATA",
      "data":{
        "amData":{
          "ecRestrictionDataNb":false,
          "iabOperationAllowed":false,
          "nssai":{
            "defaultSingleNssais":[
              {
                "sd":"000001",
                "sst":1
              }
            ]
          },
          "nssaiInclusionAllowed":false,
          "sorafRetrieval":false,
          "subscribedUeAmbr":{
            "downlink":"1 Gbps",
            "uplink":"1 Gbps"
          }
        },
        "smData":[
          {
            "dnnConfigurations":{
              "edge":{
                "5gQosProfile":{
                  "5qi":5,
                  "arp":{
                    "preemptCap":"NOT_PREEMPT",
                    "preemptVuln":"NOT_PREEMPTABLE",
                    "priorityLevel":5
                  },
                  "priorityLevel":5
                },
                "atsssAllowed":true,
                "pduSessionTypes":{
                  "allowedSessionTypes":[
                    "IPV4",
```

```
        "IPV4V6",
        "IPV6"
    ],
    "defaultSessionType": "IPV4V6"
},
"sessionAmbr": {
    "downlink": "1 Gbps",
    "uplink": "1 Gbps"
},
"sscModes": {
    "allowedSscModes": [
        "SSC_MODE_1",
        "SSC_MODE_2"
    ],
    "defaultSscMode": "SSC_MODE_2"
}
},
"ims": {
    "5gQosProfile": {
        "5qi": 5,
        "arp": {
            "preemptCap": "NOT_PREEMPT",
            "preemptVuln": "NOT_PREEMPTABLE",
            "priorityLevel": 5
        },
        "priorityLevel": 5
    },
    "atsssAllowed": true,
    "pduSessionTypes": {
        "allowedSessionTypes": [
            "IPV4",
            "IPV4V6",
            "IPV6"
        ],
        "defaultSessionType": "IPV6"
    },
    "sessionAmbr": {
        "downlink": "1 Gbps",
        "uplink": "1 Gbps"
    },
    "sscModes": {
        "allowedSscModes": [
            "SSC_MODE_1",
            "SSC_MODE_2"
        ],
```

```
        "defaultSscMode": "SSC_MODE_1"
    }
},
"internet": {
    "5gQosProfile": {
        "5qi": 5,
        "arp": {
            "preemptCap": "NOT_PREEMPT",
            "preemptVuln": "NOT_PREEMPTABLE",
            "priorityLevel": 5
        },
        "priorityLevel": 5
    },
    "atsssAllowed": true,
    "pduSessionTypes": {
        "allowedSessionTypes": [
            "IPV4V6",
            "IPV4",
            "IPV6"
        ],
        "defaultSessionType": "IPV4"
    },
    "sessionAmbr": {
        "downlink": "1 Gbps",
        "uplink": "1 Gbps"
    },
    "sscModes": {
        "allowedSscModes": [
            "SSC_MODE_1",
            "SSC_MODE_2"
        ],
        "defaultSscMode": "SSC_MODE_1"
    }
},
"local": {
    "5gQosProfile": {
        "5qi": 5,
        "arp": {
            "preemptCap": "NOT_PREEMPT",
            "preemptVuln": "NOT_PREEMPTABLE",
            "priorityLevel": 5
        },
        "priorityLevel": 5
    },
    "atsssAllowed": true,
```

```
"pduSessionTypes":{
  "allowedSessionTypes":[
    "IPV4",
    "IPV4V6",
    "IPV6"
  ],
  "defaultSessionType":"IPV4V6"
},
"sessionAmbr":{
  "downlink":"1 Gbps",
  "uplink":"1 Gbps"
},
"sscModes":{
  "allowedSscModes":[
    "SSC_MODE_1",
    "SSC_MODE_2"
  ],
  "defaultSscMode":"SSC_MODE_2"
}
},
"singleNssai":{
  "sd":"000001",
  "sst":1
}
},
"smfSelData":{
  "subscribedSnssaiInfos":{
    "1-000001":{
      "dnnInfos":[
        {
          "defaultDnnIndicator":true,
          "dnn":"internet"
        },
        {
          "defaultDnnIndicator":false,
          "dnn":"ims"
        },
        {
          "defaultDnnIndicator":false,
          "dnn":"local"
        },
        {
          "defaultDnnIndicator":false,
```



```
        "priorityLevel":5
    },
    "priorityLevel":5
},
"atsssAllowed":true,
"pduSessionTypes":{
    "allowedSessionTypes":[
        "IPV4",
        "IPV4V6",
        "IPV6"
    ],
    "defaultSessionType":"IPV4V6"
},
"sessionAmbr":{
    "downlink":"1 Gbps",
    "uplink":"1 Gbps"
},
"sscModes":{
    "allowedSscModes":[
        "SSC_MODE_1",
        "SSC_MODE_2"
    ],
    "defaultSscMode":"SSC_MODE_2"
}
},
"ims":{
    "5gQosProfile":{
        "5qi":5,
        "arp":{
            "preemptCap":"NOT_PREEMPT",
            "preemptVuln":"NOT_PREEMPTABLE",
            "priorityLevel":5
        },
        "priorityLevel":5
    },
    "atsssAllowed":true,
    "pduSessionTypes":{
        "allowedSessionTypes":[
            "IPV4",
            "IPV4V6",
            "IPV6"
        ],
        "defaultSessionType":"IPV6"
    },
    "sessionAmbr":{
```

```
        "downlink": "1 Gbps",
        "uplink": "1 Gbps"
    },
    "sscModes": {
        "allowedSscModes": [
            "SSC_MODE_1",
            "SSC_MODE_2"
        ],
        "defaultSscMode": "SSC_MODE_1"
    }
},
"internet": {
    "5gQosProfile": {
        "5qi": 5,
        "arp": {
            "preemptCap": "NOT_PREEMPT",
            "preemptVuln": "NOT_PREEMPTABLE",
            "priorityLevel": 5
        },
        "priorityLevel": 5
    },
    "atsssAllowed": true,
    "pduSessionTypes": {
        "allowedSessionTypes": [
            "IPV4V6",
            "IPV4",
            "IPV6"
        ],
        "defaultSessionType": "IPV4"
    },
    "sessionAmbr": {
        "downlink": "1 Gbps",
        "uplink": "1 Gbps"
    },
    "sscModes": {
        "allowedSscModes": [
            "SSC_MODE_1",
            "SSC_MODE_2"
        ],
        "defaultSscMode": "SSC_MODE_1"
    }
},
"local": {
    "5gQosProfile": {
        "5qi": 5,
```

```

        "arp":{
            "preemptCap":"NOT_PREEMPT",
            "preemptVuln":"NOT_PREEMPTABLE",
            "priorityLevel":5
        },
        "priorityLevel":5
    },
    "atsssAllowed":true,
    "pduSessionTypes":{
        "allowedSessionTypes":[
            "IPV4",
            "IPV4V6",
            "IPV6"
        ],
        "defaultSessionType":"IPV4V6"
    },
    "sessionAmbr":{
        "downlink":"1 Gbps",
        "uplink":"1 Gbps"
    },
    "sscModes":{
        "allowedSscModes":[
            "SSC_MODE_1",
            "SSC_MODE_2"
        ],
        "defaultSscMode":"SSC_MODE_2"
    }
}
},
"singleNssai":{
    "sd":"000001",
    "sst":1
}
}
],
"smfSelData":{
    "subscribedSnsaiInfos":{
        "1-000001":{
            "dnnInfos":[
                {
                    "defaultDnnIndicator":true,
                    "dnn":"internet"
                },
                {
                    "defaultDnnIndicator":false,

```

```
        "dnn": "ims"
      },
      {
        "defaultDnnIndicator": false,
        "dnn": "local"
      },
      {
        "defaultDnnIndicator": false,
        "dnn": "edge"
      }
    ]
  }
}
}
```